

Deliverable D6.7

Pilot (FR) Technical report and achieved results (2 | 2)

Deliverable report

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analyzing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analyzed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allow a close follow-up of the main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them throughout the whole project activities. Among potential social risks, the impact on the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

To ensure a successful implementation of the developed technologies in the pilot sites, social risks identified in WP7 for each pilot have been carefully considered. WP6 also includes the assessment and monitoring of relevant KPIs, which will help reduce the risk of work accidents and minimize the environmental impact.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
BIM	Building Information Modelling
H&S	Health and Safety
PC	Personal computer
AL3	feeder belt 3
C1, C2, C3	Screen sieve 1, 2, 3
K1	Crusher 1
Cy3	Cycloning 3
Cv3	Tank 3
TR1, TR2, ...	"Rolled" conveyor belt 1, 2
TC1, TC2, ...	"crushed" conveyor belt
KTA	Key Technology Area
dB	Decibel
CAN	Controller area network
PM2.5, PM10	Particulate matter, inhalable coarse particles with a diameter of 10/2.5 micrometres or less

1 Pilot overview

Granulats VICAT's quarry represents 10,3 % of quarries across Europe. It is specialized in raw materials recycling. It has a treatment plant where materials are inspected, washed, crushed, and stocked. The site has acquired a new washing system consisting of water tanks and pumps that allow us to recycle 90% of our water. Our main objective is to be able to predict and organize stock.

GRANULATS VICAT operates more than 40 quarries in France and 40 platforms. Very involved in the circular economy, 60 % of its sites among which the Fenouillet site participate to the recovery of construction and demolition wastes: recycling platforms or quarry's restoration made with external materials from job sites (earthworks, etc.). in terms of membership and clustering, the site in Fenouillet is an urban quarry. This a 46 000 M² place with neighbours such as Decathlon, Mc Donald, King Jouet, etc. This quarry has the particularity of not having any extraction site linked. It only works by recovering raw materials issued from local earthworks.

Here, the focus will then be on optimizing production by establishing a preventive maintenance strategy. To do so, we must put in place tools that will help us prevent machine breakdowns and unexpected curative maintenance. In the scope of the project, it is expected to be installed or put in place:

- Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS)
- A BIM model for predictive maintenance.
- Innovative mobile crusher.
- Environmental and energy consumption simulation platform.
- Weighting systems equipped with monitoring sensors linked to the SCADA.
- Artificial intelligence algorithms.
- A social acceptance strategy.

Figure 1 Overview of VICAT plant.

The plant's priorities are mainly social acceptance and improving treatment performances. More precisely, Vicat is concerned by KSA7.1 through a community engagement strategy for social acceptance in WP7, an innovative mobile crusher is expected to be tested on Vicat site piloted by METSO (WP3-KTA2.1) this will optimize the recovery of different types of materials coming from earthwork like recycled concrete while limiting noise emissions linked to the thermal engine as well as reducing fossil energy consumption. With WP4 partners, a BIM model is being worked on to improve predictive maintenance (KTA 4.1) and AI algorithms and cameras are being discussed to find their best usage (WP4 –KTA 4.2). Regarding Health, Safety & environmental management, an online platform has been created and is going through updates (WP5 –KTA 5.1).

2 Implemented technologies

Table 1 Technologies and strategies implemented in Vicat.

Technology	Partners involved
Innovative mobile crusher	METSO
Weighing systems equipped with sensors implemented on strategic conveyors belts	ARCO
Preventive maintenance strategy with a BIM MODEL	APP
Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS) – ICT platform, data lake, services, dashboards	AKKODIS
Build an H&S simulation model with energy consumption indicators	CHALMERS and ROCTIM
Treatment automation and production control	MAESTRO
AI algorithms and MetaQuarry	SIGMA and UPM-AI
Social acceptance strategy	ZABALA

2.1 Innovative mobile crusher

2.1.1 General Summary

The innovative mobile crusher was developed as part of *KTA2 Innovative Treatment processes* in DigiEcoQuarry by Metso. As stated in the grant agreement, comminution processes are energy-intensive and there is a need to improve the efficiency of them. The amount of air emissions, such as dust and CO₂, can be reduced by lowering the emissions of diesel-driven mobile machinery. During the project, Metso designed an innovative design for mobile crusher with new hybrid powertrain and additional technologies to minimize the dust and noise emissions. The prototype was manufactured based on existing model Lokotrack LT1213SE impactor crusher. Advanced noise and dust suppression technologies were incorporated to help comply with possibly strict environmental regulations. The VICAT site, located near urban populated areas, was therefore suitable choice for piloting this mobile crusher.

2.1.2 Activities performed since November 2023

The innovative mobile impactor crusher LT1213SE was developed and built as part of *WP2 T2.6* during project months M6-M36. One of the final efforts of the work was piloting the machine at the VICAT Toulouse quarry. Piloting of the mobile crusher differs quite much from the other implemented technologies in DEQ, as the piloting was possible only as a one-week campaign that took place in October 2024. Prior to the piloting week at VICAT, several practical preparatory tasks were undertaken during late 2023 and 2024. Due to the large number of new components in the innovative mobile crusher, a wide range of factory tests were performed at the Metso factory in Tampere, Finland before any actual crushing could be conducted. Additionally, the mobile crusher was pre-tested in Finland, where both rock (granite and limestone) and demolition waste were processed to evaluate the performance of the machine and effects of the implemented modifications. Based on the knowledge gained during these preparatory phases, a test plan for the VICAT piloting campaign was developed, and VICAT was informed of the plans.

At VICAT, the piloting week started on October 21, 2024. The mobile crusher was shipped from Metso, Tampere, Finland to Toulouse, France the previous week. Three research/test engineers from Metso travelled to Toulouse to operate the mobile crusher and perform the measurements. The feed material for the crusher, provided by VICAT, consisted of construction and demolition waste ranging in size from 0 to 1000 mm, with a lot of fines, as shown in Figure 2. Material included also a lot of steel reinforced concrete blocks with different sizes; one example shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2 Feed material for mobile crusher in VICAT pilot site.

Figure 3 Detail from feed material to be crushed in VICAT site, steel fibre reinforced concrete.

The crusher was prepared and adjusted to achieve optimal performance during the piloting. Collection of the component level CAN bus data was made. The performance of the new hybrid powertrain was monitored. Both dust and noise measurements were conducted in near surrounding area the machine.

Because the mobile crusher used was a new prototype, some technical challenges and interruptions were unavoidable. Some interruptions were caused by CAN bus errors and blockages in the crusher due to hard and stiff material. However, these challenges were managed, and substantial information was collected, with most of the tests outlined in the test plan being completed.

Figure 4 Innovative mobile crusher by Metso at the VICAT pilot site.

Figure 5 Personnel of VICAT and the Metso piloting crew.

From the 0-1000 mm feed provided, two products were made during the week;

- total of 945 tons of 0-80 mm (with 100 x 100 mm screen) and
- total of 277 tons of 0-35 mm (with 38mm grizzly screen).

Dust measurements were performed with handheld DustTrak aerosol monitor by measurer walking around the crushing site collecting data, while drone captures the entire session from above. The data is synchronized resulting in dust concentration maps (PM2.5 and PM10). Background and more details about the measurement method that was developed during the project are given in previously published deliverables of the DEQ project, D2.7 and D2.9. The measurement method for areal mapping of noise was developed by Metso within another research Horizon-project, ROTATE, and utilized during the piloting of DEQ. Results related to performance of the powertrain and efficiency of the dust and noise suppression systems were analyzed by Metso and the main findings are presented in Chapter 4 of this document. In addition, data from the piloting week was transferred to DEQ IQS using the developed integration in co-operation with AKKODIS.

2.2 Arco's weighting system

2.2.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	Weighing Systems
Overview	<p>The implementation of weighing systems in quarries has several key objectives that contribute to improving the efficiency and control of operations. Regarding the implementation of these weighing systems within the project, we can list some objectives.</p> <p>In the aggregates industry, precise control of material weighing is crucial to ensure efficient, high-quality production. At Arco Electrónica, we have focused on offering the latest innovations in continuous weighing systems for conveyor belts, a technology that has revolutionized the weighing process in the aggregates industry.</p>
Key Components	<p>Continuous weighing systems for conveyor belts use advanced technologies and sensors to accurately measure the flow of material conveyed on a belt. These systems are based on principles such as tensile force, pressure load or speed measurement to calculate the weight of materials in real time.</p> <p>ARCO manufactures on demand a special weighing trough, adapted to the customer's conveyor belt and production. We also carry out the transformation of a client's roller station into a weighing trough, analysing and transforming the metal support adapted to the mechanical needs of the conveyor belt to be installed.</p>
Target Audience	The main target is companies in the mining and construction sectors. Quarries, aggregate processing plants, etc.
Hardware Requirements	To implement the weighing systems, it is essential to have a conveyor belt in good condition to implement the weighing system. Both the bowl and the encoder will be placed on this belt, which will then be connected to the AE-9220V2 control unit.
Installation Process	<p>The weighing systems placed on the conveyor belts are connected by means of a 2X2X0.5mm² shielded cable reinforced with a PG-21 steel tube to the corresponding control room.</p> <p>Two weighing systems were connected to two AE-9220 V2 control equipment located in an electrical cabinet located in the control room of the pilot plant.</p>
Communication Protocols	<p>Ethernet for file exchange with PC.</p> <p>Configurable analog output.</p> <p>RS-485 and CAN for process integration.</p>
Data Storage & Management	Once the data is collected, it is stored on the AE-9220V2 device itself, with the option to export it. If you also purchase the Arco Monitor software, the data will be stored on Arco's servers. Once received, it is stored, processed, and integrated into the reporting system. All

	data is stored in our cloud system and is protected by regulatory compliance and backup policies.
AI Integration & Implementation	Models used with AI for machine learning and deep learning are being developed and incorporated into a testing phase.
Application Features	<p>High accuracy starting at 0.25%.</p> <p>Robust structure adaptable to multiple applications.</p> <p>Wide production range from 25 to 2,000 t/h, depending on the model.</p> <p>Double flexure load cell.</p> <p>Wear-resistant wheel for speed measurement, installed with a coupling arm.</p> <p>Equipment designed for continuous weighing process control and visualization.</p>
Security & Compliance	Hardware protected against unauthorized access and cybersecurity measures to protect hardware and data.
Performance Metrics	<p>Instantaneous flow rate</p> <p>Belt speed</p> <p>Production:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Partial (t/h) - Day (t/h) - Instantaneous (t/h) - Cumulative (t/h) - 3-shift work log
Support & Maintenance	Technical support, training, and assistance, both on-site and remote. KPI monitoring integration into various reporting systems. Sales, upselling, and marketing activities for commercialization.
Business Model & Pricing	The price of weighing systems depends on the dimensions of each belt where it will be installed, as well as the distance between the cabinet and the AE-9220V2 equipment. Each project has its own characteristics.
Competitive Advantage	The integrated belt weighing system is developed exclusively by ARCO. It is a solution for monitoring and controlling plants or quarries that can be installed with minimal production downtime. Furthermore, the AE-9220V2 display and control equipment is designed and manufactured by Arco, making connection simple and intuitive. Remote or on-site support is virtually immediate, assisting the end user in the event of any incident.
Future Enhancements	Improvements to the graphical process

	Improvement of AI algorithms Integration of new KPIs Improvement of the reporting system and its export
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2.2.2 Activities performed since November 2023

During May 2024, we suffered a burglary with the theft of the Arco PC as well as the installation's power cables.

We got a new computer and got the work done.

Since the installation was put back into service, we can once again increase the production tonnages of the 4/14 MRL and 11/22 MRL belts.

2.3 StatCam- ABAUT monitoring system

2.3.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	StatCam
Overview	Supervision and monitoring system for the inbound-outbound logistics.
Key Components	Hardware Installation: Setting up physical pole for installing the camera together with its power supply unit. Communications: The system transmits the camera information to our servers for being analysed and integrated in the expert system
Target Audience	Mining and construction companies
Hardware Requirements	Hardware: StatCam unit from about with terrestrial communication possibility for transmitting the information collected Software: Access to internet for accessing the expert system
Installation Process	Installation of the camera orientated to the entrance or area of interest with access to terrestrial communication Definition of the entry area via line deployment Analysis and first results adjustments
Communication Protocols -	Communication based on terrestrial communication [e.g., 3-4-5G]
Data Storage & Management	Cloud storage and cloud services for accessing to the expert system Data security, backup, and compliance considerations.
AI Integration & Implementation	AI models based on machine learning and computer vision. The results are based on the analytics provided the different recognition algorithms deployed
Application Features	AI-powered application User interface access via cloud services.
Security & Compliance	Cybersecurity measures to protect hardware and data. Compliance with industry regulations (GDPR, etc.).
Performance Metrics	KPIs based on: Truck detection [type and plate number] Material identification [filling level and material transported] Time of the detection [timestamp] Driving direction of the truck [entering or leaving the site]
Support & Maintenance	Ongoing technical support, updates over-the-air, training and

Business Model & Pricing	Saas model with a long-term contract
Competitive Advantage	The system can be installed by the local team without the need of sending any technician. In addition, the system works since the moment it is installed and the access to the results is done via any device.
Future Enhancements	Further AI – Computer vision upgrades for detecting different objects or activities

2.3.2 Activities performed since November 2023

The installation of the camera for monitoring the inbound-outbound logistics is providing relevant insights regarding the type of material transported to the pilot site.

The camera installed at the entrance of mine, is installed in a pole for visualizing the content of the dump body of the truck at its reception. The material that can be handled in the pilot site can differ from its origin. To correctly process the material, it is needed to classify first what has been transported and correctly stored it for its later processing.

The idea of the camera is to really identify that the material that is received at the pilot site correspond with the description of the material described on its transportation order. In addition, the material can contain some other pollutants in their transported material [e.g., wood material together with the concrete] that we intend to identify and report.

The camera installation is done following the principal of being orientated to the dump body of the truck, see image below.

Figure 6 View of StatCam

After the installation of the camera in the pole system and correctly orientated, the system automatically transfers the different images using a M2M Sim Card to our servers on which the information is processed, analysed and integrated in about's expert system.

The results, available after its analysing, it is possible to observe the loading level and the type of material, number of enters or exits, type of material transported and its picture together with the detection time, type of vehicle used and the picture visualizing the truck.

Figure 7 Visualization of the results

2.4 ICT platform design and implementation

The ICT platform in fact is not specific to a given quarry. In D4.2, titled “Report on IQS Design and Architecture,” the design and architecture of the Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS), developed by AKKODIS, are described. The implementation of this architecture and site’s specific development were described in D4.6 “Report on IQS, Services Integration and deployment”. Hence, more details could be found as follow:

- The IQS components currently deployed, their main functions and availability for each pilot site, are described in section 3.1 of D4.3
- The Centralized data management platform and the CDMP front-end are described in section 3.2 of D4.3
- Transport service, Plant production service, Environmental data management service, Health and safety service are described in section 3.2.3 of D4.6
- Business management tools Section 3.4 of D4.6
- The data lake, the databases, the IoT platform and Talend integration are described respectively in section 3.2.4, 3.2.5, 3.2.6 and 3.2.7 of D4.6
- The data connectors are described in section 3.3 of D4.6

The following 2 figures show the front-end welcome page, the Shared data screen and the plant production screen created for VICAT.

Figure 8 CDMP Front-End: Welcome page – “Home” screen.

Figure 9 CDMP Front-End – “Shared Data” screen.

In Vicat, several quarry processes (Automation, Environment, H&S, Mobile Crusher) have been implemented within the IQS, and their data models have been defined. Connections using REST APIs have been created, enabling direct communication for data exchange between the expert systems and the IQS according to a newly defined common data format.

The data integration process has been implemented. Data are flowing at various frequencies (daily, monthly) depending on the use case. Data integration was achieved using a proxy design pattern adopted by all data providers to push data from Vicat’s plant production developed by Arco/Maestro, H&S system of ITK, Mobile crusher system of Metso and PlantSmith system of Roctim to the IQS and to pull data from the IQS by the data consumers. The final result of the IQS data integration within the project across all sites including the data availability status in the data lake is described in section 4 of D4.6.

In addition to the reporting tools provided by the expert systems, the IQS leveraged the Power BI ecosystem to create comprehensive dashboards and reports that provide insights into KPIs from different facets of quarrying. These tools break down data silos and facilitate data integration from diverse sources, enhancing decision-making capabilities and performance monitoring. The dashboards are described in section 4.3 of D4.2 and in section 3 of D4.6.

All the dashboards created for Vicat site are accessible in one power-bi application accessible to pilot site’s users as shown in next figure.

Figure 10 DEQ Power BI App for Vicat

2.5 BIM Model

2.5.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	BIM Integration & Management
Overview	Implement Building Information Modeling (BIM) for enhanced operational efficiency at the Vicat Fenouillet recycling plant, focusing on proactive preventive maintenance and asset management to address plant shutdowns. Develop 3D models of the plant, integrate asset data, and create a 4D BIM plan centered on maintenance

	schedules and site rounds. Establish a model-based Common Data Environment (CDE) as a Digital Twin, integrating real-time data for visualization and analysis.
Key Components	<p>3D BIM Models: IFC format models of the old treatment plant, new washing plant, and site topography.</p> <p>4D BIM Planning Tool: Asta Powerproject software integrating the BIM model with preventive maintenance schedules and site round checklists derived from VICAT's data.</p> <p>Mobile Application: App for site personnel to track and update maintenance/round tasks, syncs with the 4D plan.</p> <p>CDE Platform: Autodesk Tandem used as a central repository, linking BIM models with static asset data and dynamic operational data from the DataLake.</p> <p>Data Integrator: Custom tool to fetch data from the DataLake API and feed it into the CDE.</p>
Target Audience	Quarry/Recycling Plant Management, Maintenance Teams, Site Operators.
Hardware Requirements	<p>For CDE/4D Plan access: Standard PC with internet access.</p> <p>For Mobile App: Compatible smartphone (details not specified, assumed standard Android/iOS).</p>
Installation Process	<p>3D/4D Model & CDE Setup: Performed by APP Consultoria, involving model creation/conversion, schedule development, linking, CDE configuration, and DataLake integration setup.</p> <p>Mobile App: Assumed standard app installation process for users.</p>
Communication Protocols -	<p>DataLake to CDE: HTTPS via API calls by the integrator.</p> <p>Mobile App to 4D Plan: Assumed HTTPS/cloud sync.</p> <p>User Access to CDE: Standard HTTPS.</p>
Data Storage & Management	<p>CDE Data: Stored within Autodesk Tandem (cloud platform), includes model geometry, static asset data, and ingested dynamic data from DataLake.</p> <p>Mobile App Data: User inputs stored temporarily on device, synced to central system.</p> <p>DataLake: External repository managed by AKKODIS, CDE pulls data from it.</p>
Application Features	<p>BIM Model: Detailed 3D representation of plant assets.</p> <p>4D Planning: Visualisation of maintenance schedule linked to model; task management.</p> <p>Mobile App: Easy task tracking for rounds/maintenance, status updates, photo/note uploads, urgency flagging.</p> <p>CDE: Interactive 3D model navigation (walk-through), asset data viewing (static & dynamic), data filtering, saved views, customizable dashboards.</p>
Security & Compliance	CDE Access: Managed via Autodesk Tandem user authentication.

	Mobile App: User authentication assumed. Data privacy for user inputs considered (though specifics not detailed in D4.5).
Performance Metrics	<p>Maintenance Compliance: Tracking completion rates of scheduled preventive maintenance and rounds via the app/4D plan.</p> <p>Data Availability: Monitoring successful data integration from DataLake to CDE.</p> <p>System Usage: Tracking adoption/use of the mobile app and CDE by site personnel (future metric).</p>
Support & Maintenance	APP Consultoría provides training and support for the CDE and associated tools during the pilot phase.
Business Model & Pricing	Subscription-based (less than 150k euro/year -> approx. 20k Euro for the software licenses and 120k Euro for the maintenance and update of services).
Competitive Advantage	Tailored solution addressing Vicat's specific need for streamlined preventive maintenance management. Integration of BIM, 4D scheduling, mobile app, and CDE/Digital Twin provides a holistic view of assets and maintenance status. User-friendly mobile interface designed for site personnel.
Future Enhancements	Full integration and validation of real-time data flow. Expansion of CDE dashboards. Potential use of CDE data for further predictive maintenance analytics (beyond the current scope). Refinement of mobile app based on user feedback.

2.5.2 Activities performed since November 2023

Following the initial BIM model development detailed in D4.5, work focused on refining the 4D BIM Planning tool specifically for Vicat's maintenance needs and deploying the CDE.

- **4D Preventive Maintenance Programme:** The maintenance programme, incorporating VICAT's existing maintenance sheets and round checklists, was finalized within the 4D planning tool (Asta Powerproject). Tasks were structured by asset (e.g., conveyor belts) with defined periodicities.
- **Mobile Application Integration:** A user-friendly mobile application was developed and linked to the 4D planning tool to facilitate easy progress tracking of maintenance rounds and checks by site personnel. The app allows users to view due tasks, record completion, note asset status (good/acceptable/bad), indicate urgency, add notes/images, and submit the data back to the central system.
- **CDE / Digital Twin Deployment:** The Vicat-specific BIM model was uploaded to Autodesk Tandem. Static asset data (manufacturer, model, maintenance periods, documents) was incorporated. An integrator was set up to pull dynamic data (production, consumption, machinery cycles) from the DataLake at regular intervals (every 12 hours for the pilot phase) and link it to the corresponding assets in the CDE. Customized data dashboards were created within the CDE to visualize asset data completeness and operational KPIs. Access was provided to the Vicat management team for familiarization and testing.

2.6 Treatment automation and production control

2.6.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	[Insert Service Name]
Overview	Brief summary of the service and its purpose.
Key Components	Hardware Installation: Setting up physical infrastructure. Communications: Enabling data transmission and network integration. - Data Storage: Secure cloud or on-premises storage solutions. - AI Implementation: Deploying AI-driven applications for automation and insights.
Target Audience	Define the industries or customers that benefit from this service.
Hardware Requirements	List of necessary devices (e.g., sensors, servers, IoT devices, networking equipment).
Installation Process	Step-by-step hardware setup and integration process.
Communication Protocols -	Types of communication technologies used (e.g., 5G, Wi-Fi, Ethernet, LoRa). - Data transmission security measures.
Data Storage & Management	- Storage solutions (cloud, hybrid, on-premises). - Data security, backup, and compliance considerations.
AI Integration & Implementation	- AI models used (e.g., machine learning, deep learning, NLP, computer vision). - How AI enhances application functionality (automation, predictions, analytics).
Application Features	- Core functionalities of the AI-powered application. - User interface and user experience design considerations.
Security & Compliance	- Cybersecurity measures to protect hardware and data. - Compliance with industry regulations (GDPR, HIPAA, etc.).
Performance Metrics	- KPIs to measure success (e.g., system uptime, AI model accuracy, data processing speed).
Support & Maintenance	- Ongoing technical support, updates, and troubleshooting processes.
Business Model & Pricing	- Subscription-based, pay-per-use, or one-time purchase pricing models.
Competitive Advantage	How this service stands out compared to competitors.
Future Enhancements	- Planned upgrades or AI improvements.

2.7 AI Services and MetaQuarry

The AI services designed in the project are summarised in the following table mentioning the pilot quarry they belong to:

Table 2 AI Services developed for the different pilots.

AI Service Area	Pilot site	SIGMA	UPM-AI
Hawkeye (CV) COLORIMETRY (QUAL)	CEMEX	X	X
Hawkeye (CV) GRAIN SIZE	CEMEX	X	X
Stock Forecast (CV) STOCKPILE VOLUME	Holcim & Vicat	X	X
Predictive Maintenance (PrMa) - ANOMALIES DETECTION (Acoustic&video&...)	CSI	X	X
Metaquarry (Document Mgt)	Holcim & Vicat	X	
Consumptions & production forecast	CIMPOR	X	X

In this deliverable, only those pertaining to Vicat Fenouillet’s quarry are described.

It is important to mention that the deliverable D4.3, “Report on the AI Algorithms and Services,” contains detailed design specifications, and the contents here are, in some cases, a summary of the text in the deliverable.

2.7.1 Stockpile Volume calculation

2.7.1.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	Stockpile volume calculation
Overview	<p>The Stockpile volume calculation service aims to integrate visual and data inputs to estimate the volume of the different piles to keep track of the stock available in the quarry. This service is being implemented in Vicat-Fenouillet and HOLCIM-Pioltello quarries in which some stockpiles with different grain sizes are produced. This information and will aid operators and quarry managers in optimizing plant production and multiple other scenarios, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resource Management: Accurate volume monitoring allows quarries to manage their available resources efficiently. It helps keep an up-to-date

inventory of the stockpile of materials, ensuring that adequate quantities are available to meet customer demands.

- **Inventory Control:** By tracking stockpile volumes, quarries can avoid overstocking or understocking issues. This translates to reduced waste, optimized stock levels, and cost savings regarding inventory management.
- **Quality Control:** It helps identify potential issues such as material segregation, moisture content variation, and contamination. This early detection aids in maintaining product quality standards.
- **Safety and Compliance:** It's crucial to ensure the safety of workers and adherence to environmental regulations in quarries. Monitoring stockpile volumes helps prevent hazardous overloading situations and compliance with industry regulations.
- **Predictive Analysis:** By continuously monitoring stockpile volumes, quarries can gain insights into the material consumption rate and forecast when a new extraction or shipment will be required. This proactive approach aids in planning and scheduling.

A conceptualization of the service is depicted in Figure 11 on actual images from various sites. Subfigures a) and c) illustrate the match between the actual piles in the original photographs and their reconstructed 3D models on two different sites. Subfigure d) provides a heatmap on the top view of the site in b) that matches the colour gradient to piles and terrain height. Finally, e) provides a side view of different piles for a single site, including estimations on their corresponding volumes.

Figure 11 Conceptualization of the service: from visual inputs to volume estimations.

The service calculates the volume of the piles using ground multi-view images obtained through multipoint smartphone data. For this purpose, an APP for smartphones was developed. The service can interpolate volumes, and the output is a single, site-, pile-, and time-referenced numeric value. The historical sequences for a pile or a plant shall describe stock evolution and should be possible to retrieve from the DEQ information system.

The required precision on the stockpiles is above 95% in volume. This requirement was validated during discussions with the different sites involved in the DEQ project

	<p>while defining the service and the performance level required. The acquired data encompass geo-referenced visual input(s).</p> <p>A short guideline to collect smartphone video footage using two APPs (Sensor Logger (Google, 2023), and Open Camera (Google, 2023)) was developed. These allowed tests on the reconstruction of the piles using controlled video acquisition conditions and rough GPS data (Open Camera) and to incorporate pose information to speed up the reconstruction process from sensor data (Sensor Logger). Nevertheless, scarce GPS and video footage should be enough for pile reconstruction, though much is gained when additional data is available. For this reason, the service was designed to handle diverse data sources.</p>
<p>Key Components</p>	<p>Smartphone (or drone data, or satellite, or multi-camera): to collect the georeferenced video footage around the piles.</p> <p>Communications: The smartphone app must upload the video footage to the cloud for processing. Optimisations may mitigate data exchange running on an Internet connection. Video data can be flushed whenever the quarry operator asks. Additional configurations can restrict data uploading.</p> <p>Back-end servers: Incorporate an API to operate, manage users and data, and upload video footage. The latter is processed by the AI modules.</p> <p>Data storage and processing: The massive video footage must be uploaded and processed. Due to the size of the video data, the service preserves this information for a limited amount of time. The results and pieces of evidence of the volume computation are significantly less demanding.</p> <p>AI implementation: It is integrated into the back-end servers, including GPU acceleration. The current version of the solution includes trained models that could operate without further training.</p> <p>A general Architecture diagram is appended:</p> <p>Figure 12 General Architecture for the Stockpile Volume Calculation service.</p> <p>Only service outputs, from the data lake to the dashboards and other services, are served to the IQS infrastructures.</p>

<p>Target Audience</p>	<p>The solution is intended for the quarry management teams. Quarry managers can collect evidence on producing and storing materials of different qualities and piles. Business managers have direct access to production information.</p> <p>Additionally, the service is intended for other audiences, including those acquiring raw materials and project managers using these materials.</p> <p>Furthermore, the technology developed for this service focuses on digitalising 3D structures. Such capabilities can also be used in other businesses involved in data digitalisation.</p>
<p>Hardware Requirements</p>	<p>Smartphone (currently only Android is supported).</p> <p>Alternatively, the AI system supports other georeferenced video and multi-view images, including drone flights and satellites.</p> <p>For rapid processing, the back-end service must be powered by a GPU. This component accelerates the processing of video frames and expedites the volume computation process. Without acceleration, the processing time increases to 20x, delaying output delivery. The GPU must be integrated into the back-end.</p>
<p>Installation Process</p>	<p>No installation is required at the quarry site.</p> <p>The solution requires deploying a full backend that incorporates all capabilities, including user management, data processing, and data exchange with the IQS infrastructures, which include DEQ Data Lake and Data Warehouse. The backend operates as a cloud infrastructure.</p>
<p>Communication Protocols -</p>	<p>5G or Wi-Fi. Wi-Fi connection on the smartphone data may be preferred for uploading video footage due to the amount of data involved. Several different videos can be uploaded after they have been collected. They remain on the operator's smartphone, labelled pending in the APP.</p>
<p>Data Storage & Management</p>	<p>Data is stored on operators' smartphones and backend servers. The latter is currently operating as a cloud solution for the service but is installed on UPM premises. We have tested several cloud solutions and found no restrictions for future deployments after the project is completed.</p> <p>Results are served to the IQS infrastructure for storage, backup, etc.</p>
<p>AI Integration & Implementation</p>	<p>We use AI capabilities to process video footage, digitalize the stockpiles, and compute the volumes. AI models provide computer vision capabilities, segmentation, illumination and location correction, enhanced multiview matching, as well as optimized 3D computation, and shape correction.</p>
<p>Application Features</p>	<p>The service can build a <u>complete 3D model from georeferenced video</u> footage or image sequences. This can be collected using smartphones or other unmanned vehicles. Despite the limitations and spurious effects of smartphone GPS data and video quality, the models are successfully produced. The depth and resolution of 3D models may be adjusted for different applications. For this particular service on stockpile volume calculation, low-density meshed models are preferred to expedite the volume calculation.</p> <p>This service has three <u>user interfaces</u>.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The APP is the main interface for interacting with the collected data, the evidence, and the results obtained on the stockpile volume. We have implemented two different APPS:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The data acquisition APP is used as a measuring solution to run tests and demonstrate the functionalities. This APP should no longer be needed as these functionalities will be included in the following ones. ▪ The user APP. This included extended capabilities to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Create new accounts ▪ Recover the user password and set access credentials ▪ APP full navigation, including historical data, video footage collection, results presentation, user profile and management. ▪ Receiving notifications: new tasks, new videos to process, new processing completed with new results. ▪ The complementary Web version of the APP is to be completed to ease interaction and provide a complete service experience: full registration, access to reports, export data, invoicing, etc. ▪ The service's dashboard provides access to the detailed information uploaded to the Data Lake and the Data Warehouse. The PowerBI dashboard only provides a summary of the results obtained.
<p>Security & Compliance</p>	<p>The app uses token-based authentication for secure user identification. A single sign-on approach has been implemented, which may also be used on the web-based interface. We used Google's Firebase Firestore NoSQL database and Firestore Authentication. Tests were conducted on a free account, including user and data management.</p> <p>Furthermore, the APP defines different roles associated with different privileges. The list of roles includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ADMIN (for the account/company manager) with unrestricted access and additional access requirements: two-factor authentication. ▪ MANAGER (for the quarry manager) has no control over the company account, is designated by the ADMIN, can generate lower-level profiles, define tasks, and assign them. ▪ OPERATOR (for quarry operators) manages the data acquisition process on their own or in response to a task assigned by a MANAGER. ▪ TEST USER (newbies): Any user can download the app and learn more about it. However, those who request a demo will get a code to unveil the app's demo functionalities. Demo features are restricted from the cloud side and can include all role levels if this is approved. <p>None of the information required for this service is related to the GDPR. Nevertheless, no user information, including contact details, is stored in the APP or the system.</p> <p>No specific security measures have been placed on the APP-collected data, as this is regarded as non-critical information. Videos are not encrypted nor protected in any specific way within the user's smartphone.</p> <p>Data exchange uses HTTPS-protected connections on the APIs to preserve privacy on the unchanged data, particularly any user-specific information that is exchanged, including user and service tokens.</p>
<p>Performance Metrics</p>	<p><u>System up-time</u> (on the server side): intended for 24/7. In practice, the Service Level Agreement (SLA) should cover up to 95% of up-time.</p> <p><u>Accuracy in volume estimation</u>: Discussions within the DEQ workforce suggest a minimum accuracy of 95% for a valuable solution. Tests conducted at this point were</p>

	<p>above 98% accuracy. Compared with other solutions available on the market, the accuracy level is the same as obtained by trained technicians and drone-flight data.</p> <p><u>Data processing speed</u> (per MB of video footage): A full file video (5 minutes to process) currently requires less than 10 minutes. In optimistic scenarios (high-quality footage), it goes down to 5 minutes (1:1). For low-quality footage, processing time increases (up to 1:2).</p> <p><u>Number of monthly active users</u> (MAUs): A larger number of users is key to lead generation and increased service use. We intend to track the number of visits to the service, the recursive use of the volume estimation feature, and historical data consultation and exporting. These metrics can be computed but will not be tracked until the Android app version is published and open to the market.</p> <p><u>Versatility</u>. The solution is device-agnostic. For the time being, only an Android version of the app is available. If possible, an iOS version will be developed to cover 90%+ of the smartphone market, particularly for managers and top levels.</p> <p><u>Replicability</u>. The solution can be replicated on all five continents, regardless of the applications and quarry. Tests conducted showed that stockpiles made of other materials may as well be evaluated.</p>
<p>Support & Maintenance</p>	<p>The app incorporates support and contact functionalities. During tests, no messages were communicated directly from the latest versions of the app.</p> <p>Technical support was provided through direct contact with the UPM-AI team during DEQ. In the future, this will be entirely managed through the APP.</p> <p>The service can be updated from the Android OS, the app, and the Cloud Backend. The latter connects to the app and can verify the running version of the up-to-run seamless updates with minimum user intervention. Android notifications can also suggest full app updates, as they are typically handled.</p> <p>Regular software patches need to be provided to address bugs and vulnerabilities.</p>
<p>Business Model & Pricing</p>	<p>We have developed a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) model for this service. The model is based on competitors providing similar services, though these services provide very different performance levels and features.</p> <p>The market analysis suggests we focus on early adopters among large enterprises following the DEQ project. The new stages focus on client funding and avoiding equity sharing. Organic growth on the B2B side is considered possible, while individual agents and small and medium enterprises should come in the meantime, provided that specific pricing is provided to target them.</p> <p>The estimated TAM of the mining industry worldwide may reach 2.3 billion dollars (1.0 billion dollars in the EU). SAM focuses on the 10% of companies that have expressed interest in tech solutions to this need, reaching 10,0 M dollars in the EU. Starting from DEQ, SOM could easily reach 20% of this for 2M dollars a year.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Customer segments: The service is aimed at quarrying sites or other industrial environments that require production or storage monitoring, such as farming industries, transport, etc. ▪ Value proposition: The innovation measures the volume of the piles of stored materials or products and provides and estimation of the volume. For countable items, it may be adjusted to provide a number of it. ▪ Channels: Lead generation from UPM contacts in specialised forums and contacts from associations and workgroups, including those headed by

	<p>ANEFA. Direct sales via interviews of commercial teams with IT departments. Use Sigma’s web channel and commercial offices in Madrid, London and Miami.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Customer relationships: Personalized assistance fitting customers’ needs for LEs and SMEs. The APP is meant to serve as a hub for fostering stronger customer relationships and driving engagement. It leverages user experience and support to provide data analytics and enhance the user experience. It facilitates digital scale economies by allowing businesses to reach a broader customer base without the need for physical expansion. It offers features like targeted marketing tools, user behaviour insights, and automated communication channels, enabling personalized experiences to be monitored and evaluated. <p>To boost engagement, it incorporates a user-friendly interface with intuitive navigation, real-time notifications and updates, knowledge sharing among users, and space to include other features, such as news, blogs on use, reviews of the product, and information on coming releases and how to use them.</p> <p>The app aims to become an indispensable tool for measuring stock by serving as a central platform for customer interactions and growth opportunities. It streamlines digitalization processes, ultimately contributing to increased efficiency across the market.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Revenue streams: An annual subscription fee, depending on the number of operators, plus pay-per-use as the video footage is processed. ▪ Key resources: We avoid the need for field installers or HW specialists. Only IT personnel are needed. Computation resources include cloud storage and servers for data processing. ▪ Key activities: Monitoring, data analysis, process improvement. ▪ Key partners: Customers and end users, including associations. ▪ Cost structure: Human resources for development, O&M resources, servers (storage and processing), and marketing resources. <p>The pricing model is based on two trenches:</p> <p>An <u>annual subscription</u> fee is charged to access the service, launch the account and configuration, and keep generated data throughout the years. This fee varies depending on the number of quarry sites, operators involved, and service processing speed. It may be around 1.000 – 2.000 EUR per site for consecutive years, incremented by +1.000 EUR in the first year for the setup, and in consecutive years only if specific upgrading or adaptations are required.</p> <p>A <u>pay-per-use model</u> for the stockpile volume calculation each time a video is processed. To ease this process, charging runs on the size of the uploaded video footage (megabytes of data). Final prices are to be defined after segmentation. Tentative numbers suggest these may be between 0.5 and 2.0 EUR per MB.</p> <p>Additionally, initial analyses suggest a PoC (Proof of Concept) pricing with no pay-per-use, as well as different plans, including DEMO and Freemium access. These and others may be used as tools for lead generation and other marketing strategies.</p> <p>The model's pricing will NOT include initial requirement analysis or deployment fees. O&M will be included in the annual subscription.</p>
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<p>Competitive Advantage</p>	<p>For years, the lack of digitalisation of production data was the leading competitor for such a service. Some alternatives have been used in recent years, but the number of alternatives is still quite limited. In mining, 80% are independent contractors with drones and hand-made reports. None of these provide continuous monitoring SaaS capabilities. Continuous monitoring is a costly handmade process involving digital tools that are relatively slow and typically require stopping operations.</p> <p>In the Computer Vision space, alternatives include companies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SR Measures (South Africa, 2012) uses deep learning, is multipoint, and focuses on individual piles. Its granted accuracy sits at 70%. - Moesure (UK, 2014) is the first motion-based measuring tool that utilises high-performance inertial sensors packed into a handheld device. Products currently use smartphone technology to accelerate measurements. - Trimble Access (Dubai, 2017). It uses specific HW instrumentation to collect the data and provide volume estimations. These components require proficient operators and long learning curves. - ITS Geo Solutions (Germany, 2022). Multifaceted reconstruction. Dense pointclouds construction. Clean input was collected in good capturing conditions. It requires trained operators and is under a costly subscription. <p>The developed AI service can directly operate with georeferenced data from smartphone video. The solution is device-agnostic and could be extended to other devices. The system can run 24/7, with an estimated precision of over 98% accuracy, from small piles (less than 1 cubic meter) to real large ones (several thousand). This represents a relative +25% improvement in reported accuracy while handling complex acquisition conditions. Tests conducted in DEQ suggest that inexperienced operators could easily manage the APP and that the learning curve to collect quality video footage is very rapid.</p>
<p>Future Enhancements</p>	<p>A complete user experience requires a web structure that matches the APP structure and dashboard presentation capabilities directly connected to this. For such a service to operate, we need presentation capabilities similar to those provided by the PowerBI dashboards in DEQ. A similar structure can be developed using external (cloud or in-premise) services.</p> <p>Ongoing upgrades:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Video data selection software will be integrated into the app. This capability should reduce the amount of data that needs to be exchanged. Preliminary tests are being conducted to evaluate this possibility. For example, frames providing purely redundant information could be removed. - We aim to enhance visualisations with evidence of the computed volumes, specifically on the video input and the 3D meshes that reproduce the stockpiles. The models should be reduced. To reduce storage, we may use 2D visualisations instead of full meshes. - As an extension to this evidence, generating automatic reports may be a relevant feature for many sites. Complete extension reports have been the standard output

	<p>delivered to them after stockpiles are assessed. This tool may expedite the acquisition of the technology.</p> <p>Backlog (to be evaluated):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During video acquisition, it is technically possible to run automatic data selection on the video stream. This requires specialised AI models to select relevant data for 3D reconstruction. - During video acquisition, one may like to enhance the experience of the pile recording. A completion bar based on geolocation may help operators validate the acquired data right while they are collecting the video footage. - It is possible to enrich the collected data with information about the camera's tilt and pan for programmed tasks and based on the operator's geolocation during acquisition. Preliminary tests suggest that this information expedites the volume computation process and reduces noise. - With location information and orientation referring to the operators, models can predict the operator's trajectory and restrict the line of sight for piles already identified in a given task. - We used a standard dockerised implementation on the backend servers to handle model reconstruction. Parallel processing should be achieved through a dynamically managed parameter server architecture that automatically scaled worker nodes using Kubernetes orchestration. This system would employ chain replication with relaxed consistency guarantees to maintain continuity during server failures, allowing backup parameter servers to resume operations with warm in-memory weights while preserving high GPU utilisation during downtimes. - For resource management, we aim to implement automated server lifecycle controls using CLI-based triggers to scale GPU-accelerated instances based on real-time compute demands. This will allow us to achieve significant throughput improvements.
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2.7.1.2 Activities performed since November 2023

During this time, we completed numerous milestones towards the final service productisation. The elementary capabilities required for volume computation (at prototype level, outside the laboratory) had already been validated in the previous period. In this one, we focused on building the product from the user side (data acquisition APP and results presentation) to the server (back-office) side.

Validated integrated APP: geo-referenced video on a single APP

During this period, we collaborated with the quarry sites, collecting video footage on stockpiles using two different data collection APPs and evaluating the results obtained. New video footage was collected at Vicat Fenouillet's quarry site. The video footage collected, and the results obtained were validated by all teams involved. The level of precision was found to be sufficient, as well as the details offered. From this point on, activities focused on building a fully operative prototype of the service, integrating the full APP experience and required backend.

User-oriented APP version

To proceed to the user's final design of the service app, it is essential to identify the requirements, objectives and needs a user may experience. For this, we defined eight use cases and five user stories epics. User stories, from the perspective of those who might use the system, describe what they want to achieve and the benefits they expect to obtain. On the other hand, use cases adopt a more technical perspective, detailing specific event flows and interactions between the

user and the system. The combination of user stories and use cases offers a complete understanding of the project requirements, from user needs to the technical operation of the system.

The use cases and user stories included below are not limited to presenting and visualising results but cover most parts of the service. The goal was not to overlook any aspect of users' needs and interests in the service.

Hereafter, we include a reduced analysis of the key epics identified:

Epic 1: User Account Management.

Story 1.1: As a user, I want to create an account to be able to log in

Description: The user wants to create a new account to access the application and use its features.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The user can access a registration form.
- The user can enter their data (name, email, password, etc.).
- The user can create the account and access the application once registration is complete.

Story 1.2: Exploration. As a user, I want to change the language to understand what's in the application.

Description: The user wants to change the language of the application interface to their preferred language.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application offers an option to select the interface language.
- The user can choose from a list of available languages.
- The application interface is displayed in the language selected by the user.

Story 1.3: As a user, I want to log in to use the application with my data

Description: The user wants to log into the application using their username and password.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The user can access a login form.
- The user can enter their username and password.
- The application validates the user's credentials.
- The user logs into the application and accesses its functionalities.

Story 1.4: As a user, I want to be able to reset my password in case I forget it

Description: The user wants to recover their password if they have forgotten it.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application offers an option to recover the password.
- The user can enter the email address associated with the account.
- The application sends an email to the user with a link to reset the password.
- The user can access the link and set a new password.

Story 1.5: As a user, I want to access my profile to view my data

Description: The user wants to access their profile to view their data.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The user can access a profile section within the application.
- The user's profile displays their personal data (name, email, etc.).

Story 1.6: As a user, I want to modify my profile to keep the data updated

Description: The user wants to modify their personal data in their profile.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The user can access a profile editing section within the application.

- The user can modify their personal data (name, email, etc.).
- The application validates the new data entered by the user.
- The user's personal data is correctly updated in their profile.

Epic 2: Video Management

Story 2.1: As a user, I want to be able to record videos for the data to be analysed with artificial intelligence

Description: The user wants to record a video within the application and have it analysed using artificial intelligence.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application offers a video recording function.
- The user can focus on the camera and record a video.
- The recorded video is stored in the application or sent to a server for analysis.
- Artificial intelligence analyses the video and generates relevant data.
- The user can access the analysed video data.

Story 2.2: As an operator user, I want to see the status of the videos I have made.

Description: The operator user wants to view the status of the videos they have recorded or uploaded to the platform.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application displays a list of videos with their current status (recorded, in analysis, analysis completed, error).
- The operator user can select a video to view its status in detail.
- The operator user can view the analysed data of the video if the analysis has finished.

Epic 3: Data Analysis

Story 3.1: As a manager user, I want to be able to view the analysed data of the quarry

Description: The manager user wants to view the data analysed from the videos recorded by the quarry users.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application offers a section to view the data analysed by the quarry.
- The manager user can view the data based on the desired stack or individual recordings.
- The manager user can view the analysed data as graphs.

Story 3.2: As an admin user, I want to be able to view the data analysed by the group or company.

Description: The administrator user wants to view the analysed data of the videos recorded by all users of the group or company.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application offers a section to view analysed data of the group or company.
- The administrator user can view the data based on the desired stack or quarry or individual recordings.
- The administrator user can view the analysed data as graphs.

Epic 4: User Account Management

Story 4.1: As an admin or manager user, I want to be able to manage my subordinates' accounts to expel them, assign work, or change their access level.

Description: The administrator or manager user wants to manage the accounts of their subordinates within the application.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application offers a section to manage subordinate accounts.
- The administrator or manager user can view a list of their subordinates and their associated data.
- The administrator or manager user can expel a subordinate from the application.

- The administrator or manager user can assign work to a subordinate.
- The administrator or manager user can change the access level of a subordinate (user, operator, manager, admin).

Story 4.2: As a user, I want to be able to view the work assigned to me

Description: The user wants to view the work assigned to them by an administrator or manager.

Acceptance Criteria:

The application displays a section of tasks assigned to the user.

The user can see the description of each task, its deadline, and its status (pending, completed).

The user can mark a task as completed once they have finished it.

Epic5: Error Handling

Story 5.1: As a user, I want to see what has caused an error to know what to do

Description: The user wants to receive clear and helpful information in case an error occurs in the application.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application displays a descriptive error message indicating the cause of the error.
- The error message offers the user a solution or steps to resolve the problem.
- The application logs the error for analysis by developers.

Story 5.2: As a user, I want to be able to contact support to receive help if I can't resolve the error myself.

Description: The user wants to be able to contact the application's support team if they cannot resolve an error on their own or have a particular request.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application provides an email address to contact technical support (inactive in this Final Project).
- The user can send an email.
- The support team assists the user in resolving the error.

We chose to build a React Native application using the Expo framework. The latter is ideal for developers seeking a more straightforward and faster setup, as it offers a wide range of integrated tools and supports standard features without additional configuration.

Figure 13 Class structure for the APP

We tested Firebase (Google Service from Ireland, EU) for rapid testing and validation of the development platform. All these tests will also be reproduced on other platforms and deployed within EU infrastructures. Firebase offers various backend services, such as authentication tools, real-time databases, cloud storage, and notification management. We evaluated the ease of use, access to real-time databases, existing support and documentation, and scalability. Our benchmark included AWS Amplify, Microsoft Azure, and Backendless. The class diagram that was implemented is elementary yet illustrative enough and is depicted in Figure 13.

The current version of this app includes up to nine different views, including those for user signup, login, and registration; information and data visualisations (up to 4 different views), including side information on the DEQ project; and views for data acquisition, user profiles, and account management. Figure 14 summarizes some of the most illustrative views.

The designed APP includes notification capabilities. These could be integrated with the Google Android notification system, but we kept them separate inside the APP for better control of the visualisation.

Figure 14. Visualization on the Use APP deployed. Some of the key views are depicted, including the login, workload management, task registration, and stock details.

The development of the front for this APP was partially funded by Ayuntamiento de Madrid and Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, within the Program for “FOMENTO DE LA INNOVACIÓN A TRAVÉS DE PROGRAMAS DE INCUBACIÓN, ACELERACIÓN O ESCALADO DE PROYECTOS INNOVADORES DESARROLLADOS POR UNIVERSIDADES PÚBLICAS, FUNDACIONES SIN ÁNIMO DE LUCRO VINCULADAS A UNIVERSIDADES PÚBLICAS, PARQUES CIENTÍFICOS Y ORGANISMOS PÚBLICOS DE INVESTIGACIÓN” (Promotion Of Innovation Through Incubation, Acceleration, Or Scaling Programs For Innovative Projects Developed By Public Universities, Non-Profit Foundations Linked To Public Universities, Science Parks,

And Public Research Organizations). This was awarded in May 2024, with a 3,550 EUR budget dedicated to the activities described above as part of the entrepreneurial project acopIA.

Video footage defects: analysis and correction

Sun and lens flares, light reflections, and refraction contribute to the aesthetic appeal of visual assets and set the general atmosphere, providing an artistic and dramatic element. Flares and reflections are due to a luminous source and a lens arranged at specific angles relative to the centre of the camera lens and the CCD sensor. Contrarily, diffraction appears due to a partial obstruction or a change in light propagation. Despite their visual appeal and aesthetic value, which drove early attempts to generate them artificially, these effects substantially challenge open-world data acquisition for engineering applications.

It is well-documented that significant alterations in lighting conditions profoundly impact the performance of computer vision applications. The challenge is particularly relevant when cameras cannot be positioned or adjusted due to their fixed locations or to maintain a specific viewpoint. The complexity is heightened when multiple images or video sequences are involved. The need for fixed acquisition conditions clashes with the desire to capture diverse visual perspectives, requiring innovative solutions to address flares, diffraction, and reflections.

Figure 15. The overall scheme for the proposed pipeline (central block, yellow background) and the OpenSfm processing pipeline (right block, white background) includes some examples of the processing's intermediate results.

SfM (structure-from-motion) reconstructs three-dimensional structures from a sequence of two-dimensional images or frames collected from different viewpoints. As a result, the algorithm computes estimates on the 3D geometry and camera poses and tracks. When collecting the input sequence, the latter two correspond to a moving camera's location and orientation relative to the reconstructed geometry. Input images may be discarded when the algorithm is unsuccessful in finding a match with the provided sequence. The resulting geometry and camera poses may be incomplete when the algorithm cannot find a suitable transformation, causing holes or breaks in the reconstructed 3D geometry and invalidating any posterior computation on the pile's volume.

To grasp an idea of the time required to process a video and the distribution of time along the pipeline blocks, we computed these values for a standard 440 MB MP4 footage of 175 seconds and 1920x1080 pixels per frame from our dataset with OpenSfm SIFT-GPU branch, running on a GPU-accelerated i9-9900K 64 GB CPU using a 16 GB Geforce RTX4060Ti. The percentage of time devoted to each stage is included to the right in the Figure below alongside the corresponding block. OpenSfm devotes most of its time to compute the pointclouds, mainly to the final output depth maps and only a little to the initial, low-resolution reconstruction. Once a preliminary match is achieved based on anchor points, producing the actual models optimising the reconstruction and the camera points requires a costly procedure. The better the key points match, the easier and quicker the optimisation.

Figure 16. The proposed pipeline achieves inputs (top) and outputs (bottom) in different configurations: without any preprocessing (left), with early masking (centre), and using the refined masked (right).

To validate our hypotheses and the results of our work, we conducted several experiments following the structure of the proposed pipeline. On different setups and different input data, we computed the following figures on a synthetic (with and without distortions) and a real dataset: (i) the number of successfully matched points in the SfM reconstruction on each video, (ii) the number of reconstructed point clouds and the average confidence level assigned to the reconstructed points, (iii) the percentage of reconstruction achieved.

We integrated additional Computer Vision models specifically trained to match quarry and challenging illumination conditions for this task. The original flare models had to be entirely retrained, and the data augmentation reworked to represent actual real-world conditions and produce meaningful results.

The intermediate and final outputs of the proposed pipeline for a sample frame shows that in a standard configuration where the proposed pipeline is unavailable, the input frame will be the visual input to the OpenSfm. Conversely, this frame and the computed mask are used as inputs for the OpenSfm on the proposed model. The masked input frame from the example below is included as an example.

We also evaluated the difference in the SfM reconstruction from the distorted videos using the synthetic and real-world datasets to compare the original reconstruction results and the improvements introduced by the proposed preprocessing of the video sequences. We include snapshots of the reconstructed geometries without the proposed pipeline and include the proposed masking and refined methods. The top row exemplifies the inputs to the OpenSfm on each configuration. At the bottom of the figure, the first row depicts views of the reconstructions achieved, and the second illustrates the camera tracks. The red dots correspond to these tracks, while the green ones represent GPS positions assigned to the frames while capturing the video.

Certainly, SfM reconstructions on the unprocessed video sequences are improved when using the pre-processed sequences and masks. While the original reconstructions were fed with 17% of the video frames, 2.5% of them were rejected during the reconstruction. Those frames did not include matches and could not contribute to the reconstruction. The outcome included large unreconstructed regions (21%) and significant holes. Contrarily, the preprocessing pipeline was able to select the frames appropriately, slightly increasing the number of those processed (additional 3%) while achieving an 87% with the first method proposed, involving the masks and the varying sample, and up to 99%+ for the final, refined algorithm across all the videos in our datasets.

Synthetic dataset design and implementation

We found that the current state of the art in 3D reconstruction in conditions matching quarry sites lacked a dataset for benchmarking. This is a critical problem while aiming to validate the results obtained outside the actual physical outdoor measures. Due to this limitation, we designed, implemented, and produced a synthetic dataset to be publicly shared to evaluate new solutions and future enhancements.

We generated three synthetic video sequences to qualify and quantify the impact of the effects evaluated in this contribution under controlled conditions. We built a synthetic model of a digitised pile, set it in a computed-generated outdoor daylight scenario and rendered a video while moving the camera around this pile as if the scene had been recorded using a smartphone. We also introduced the light effects observed in the previous dataset, which we had been discussing throughout this contribution. A second video was produced, including a punctual light source imitating the sun without the effects. Finally, a third video was rendered using diffuse light. The lower row of the Figure 17 includes snapshots of the rendered videos showcasing the different effects. These effects match actual conditions found on the video footage collected in the DEQ tests that were conducted, see upper row.

For this activity, we used our trained AI models for flare and glare generation and addition, which we ran on top of a generated Blender 4.2 LTS project. In this project, we defined the space for the pile, as well as the geometry and structure of the surroundings, to simulate real data acquisition conditions. These included the relative location of the sun. The software allowed us to simulate the moving operator handling the smartphone while recording the video footage. The scenario that was designed could be used in the future on other digitalized piles to validate the reconstruction and assessment process.

The dataset publication is pending as of the day this report was written. This will be publicly released as part of a contribution submitted to an international conference.

Figure 17 Snapshots of images containing the addressed visual effects.

Full processing pipeline

For estimating material stockpile volumes (or other objects), we follow a modular pipeline consisting of three main stages:

- Preprocessing: From a video capturing the stockpile (ideally encircling it completely), we execute:
 - Frame extraction: Decompose video into frames containing (or later enriched with) metadata about the capture device's position, orientation, and timestamp.
 - Intelligent frame selection: Optimize computational efficiency by selecting only frames with significant visual variance, as consecutive frames often provide redundant information.
 - Masking: Remove irrelevant regions from frames that don't contribute to reconstruction.
 - Flare and glare removal: Mitigate sun glare artefacts that significantly distort mound reconstruction accuracy.
 - Metadata handling: Add external metadata to frames if not embedded during capture.
- Reconstruction: Uses SfM algorithms:
 - Input: Pre-processed frames with the highest reconstruction relevance.
 - Output: Noisy 3D point cloud of the reconstructed stockpile/object.
- Postprocessing
 - Filtering: To remove outliers. Signal processing techniques achieve significant noise reduction.
 - Meshing: Convert filtered point cloud into a triangular mesh with vertices at reconstructed points.
 - Volume estimation: Calculate stockpile volume using the tetrahedron method from triangular mesh.

Several stages of this pipeline require GPU acceleration on the AI models. These include the intelligent frame selection, the masking, flare and glare removal, and the output denoising.

The entire processing pipeline for the video footage is illustrated in Figure 18. The referred metadata includes georeferencing, relative orientation, and position information to ease 3D reconstruction.

Figure 18 The complete processing pipeline for volume estimation.

We start from the video input, process the video sequences, and incorporate geolocation and other metadata. The following stages match the previous description of the pipeline.

Development of back-end capabilities

The back-end system consists of various interconnected modules that communicate with each other. This section will present a general architecture with all the modules. To understand the configuration of the individual modules, it is also necessary to understand their function within the system and their interconnection with other modules.

Figure 19 Summary of the infrastructure of the dockerised back-end service.

Figure 19 connects the different modules of the general architecture and their connections. Not all modules will be developed in this work, but all are important to understand the system's operation. The modules involved are:

- Service API: Python server for endpoint deployment. Very common for network deployments.
- Queue Manager: request orchestrator for queries and results. We used RabbitMQ.
- Artificial Intelligence: We used a module dedicated to calculating volumes from videos. We used an extended implementation of the OpenSfM, including the capabilities listed before.
- NoSQL Database focuses on monitoring the different processes. We used Loki + Prometheus.
- Visualisation Interface: This is used to monitor and manage requests visually. We used Grafana.

- SQL Database: This module is dedicated to responding to received requests. They must be separated from the traffic because they can arrive asynchronously to the queries.

To manage and monitor the deployment, we included Traefik to monitor the framework's overall status.

Business model formalisation

We developed and validated an entire service business model with the help of two world-class investors in this space. This activity was conducted within a Training Program for entrepreneurs organised by UPM.

Based on this service's unique features, we found a substantial opportunity (numbers in this document) and ran several simulations on cash flow and profitability under different scenarios. Results show that the proposed business model may cover the existing market needs well and identify that materials buyers and contractors developing the projects using them may share this need. These are all three faces of the same activity, and all need to control the amount of available material at an affordable and controlled price.

Moreover, companies outside the raw materials sector expressed interest during the DEQ dissemination activities. Specifically in the mining sector, where silos may be used at some point but not continuously along the value chain. In other industries, factories store the resources necessary for production in piles of different shapes and sizes. This includes food and paper production industries.

The business model was presented to the 2024 Edition of ActúaUPM Competition under the initiative for entrepreneurship acopIA. This was awarded the Top Rank project (15,000 EUR, December 2024). Previously, in this very competition, the same initiative was awarded as one of the 10 top ideas for innovation in UPM (granted 1,000 EUR, June 2024).

News: <https://www.upm.es/?id=CON16159&prefmt=articulo&fmt=detail>

2.7.2 Metaquarry

2.7.2.1 General Summary

The following table summarises the main features of the Metaquarry service that was designed for VICAT. The latter enhancements are included. The detailed specification and design can be found in D4.3 "Report on the AI Algorithms and Services".

Service Name	METAQUARRY SERVICE
Overview	<p>Quarries handle lots of documentation that is stored safely. This documentation is very diverse: contracts, administrative accounting, invoices, regulations, HR documents and a big etc. What is true, however, is that they do not produce a lot of documentation in terms of manual editing; in many cases it is still produced by hand and, subsequently digitalized. It was discovered that quarries were very interested in having advanced search capabilities in several languages to trace all sorts of information stored, in many cases, in very complex directory and server directory trees. Also, the possibility of getting summaries from the Natural language processing tool proposed by Sigma will enable their easier finding of, for instance, instructions for repairs in machine manuals, contact information for different suppliers or the date and a summary of given works being performed in the quarry by third parties.</p> <p>These tools that have been integrated into MetaQuarry will bring together in a federated way (depending on the Databases organization of the quarry information) sources of information of any nature accessible through an API and allow searches and retrieval of information from natural language queries to locate fragments and contents of interest (regulations, manuals, contracts, tutorial videos, etc.). Therefore, it was proposed that DEQ develop a system that</p>

	<p>complements the management of digital files, making use of different AI processing techniques based on NLP.</p> <p>Quarry organizations have digital files in different media (documents with text and images, videos, audios, web pages, databases, social networks, etc.) in either native or compressed formats, located in various repositories, which greatly complicates the task of searching their content without the appropriate tools. Therefore, a significant part of the company's documentation base remains hidden for consultation, analysis and exploitation tasks.</p> <p>To overcome this limitation, Sigma proposed to develop MetaQuarry a solution that will reuse the available digital repositories and will allow content to be retrieved through searches expressed in natural language and which explore any type of document previously indexed through the search engine that it incorporates. To this end, MetaQuarry is able to handle and search documents stored in different commercial or open-source cloud or private storage.</p> <p>Basically, MetaQuarry is a RAG-type (Generation Augmented Recovery) system, that combines search and language generation functionalities through LLMs (Large Language Models). On the one hand, it retrieves relevant documents, and on the other, it finds suitable answers inside these documents.</p> <p>For testing purposes in VICAT, a private cloud was customized for VICAT so that they could upload any documentation they considered of interest to use for evaluation purpose.</p>
<p>Key Components</p>	<p>A general Architecture diagram is appended:</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 20 Component architecture</i></p> <p>It is important to highlight that the components are basically running on SIGMA servers for the project's evaluation and implementation phases. The tool itself can be deployed locally if the need arises following, for example, security criteria. For VICAT, a cloud approach was adopted. The description of the different components is outlined here (Contents extracted from D4.3).</p> <p>Web Application</p> <p>The MetaQuarry web application is based on Python's Streamlit Framework and integrates with a search engine described below.</p>

Streamlit has some features that make it of great interest for such a project. It is a framework very much oriented to the field of AI data visualization and is used as a standard solution in similar solutions by the AI community.

The main functionalities of the Web Application are:

- **Authentication.** It is the initial component that allows authenticated access and cookie management natively. Authentication guarantees the security of potentially confidential information.
- **Questions:** It offers a text window in which users can write a query or question. When sending a query, the system will return a list of documents in order of relevance to the query and, whenever possible, an automated answer to the question asked, obtained by means of an LLM (Large Language Model). Next to the documents will appear a highlighted fragment, where the greatest match with the query is found and a link where the user can download the document from its original source. Questions can be formulated in natural language. Users do not need to use any special syntax to search or retrieve documents. It is also possible to filter results by language simply typing in the query: "*pdf documents on water saving in french*". Users can alternatively use the drop-down filters shown under the search window.
- **Testing:** Displays a list of 35 test questions in English and Italian manually prepared by Sigma from documents provided by VICAT to evaluate the system.
- **Documents:** Returns a list of indexed documents from the configured sources. In the case of VICAT, the number of indexed documents is 60.
- **Configuration:** It allows the user to integrate MetaQuarry with different document management platforms. Credentials obtained from these platforms are stored in a local SQLite database. Currently MetaQuarry is integrated with the following platforms:
 - Google Drive
 - Microsoft SharePoint
 - Owncloud

Natural Language Processing API

The purpose of this module is to provide Natural Language Processing functionalities to improve the search and retrieval of documents and information.

- **Language detection**

This module automatically detects the language of the query when user does not specify the language in his or her query. Detection is done using the SolR Tika component based on a previously trained and highly configurable classifier: recognizable languages can be restricted, only documents in certain languages can be indexed, etc. The language detector recognizes 49 languages with 99% accuracy.

- **Query preprocessing**

Two processes are carried out based on the user's query:

- Semantic word extraction. It is highly recommended to that you simplify the query and avoid introducing noise, such as very frequent used words of very frequent use or grammatical words: determiners, prepositions, conjunctions, etc. This task is carried out using Spacy POS Tagging pre-trained models.

- Filter detection. As mentioned above, users can specify the language or format in which they want to filter the results. These entities are recognized in queries by a simple system of rules based on linguistic patterns.

- **Language model**

As mentioned above, the Question Answering component allows the user to find answers, not just documents. To carry out this functionality, different pretrained language models fine-tuned for the question answering task have been tested and evaluated. For each of the languages in which MetaQuarry has been implemented, the model that best answered a series of questions prepared manually based on the documentation provided by the pilot mines has been chosen.

The selected models are the following:

- English: deepset/tinyroberta-squad2 (HuggingFace, 2023).
- French: etalab-ia/camembert-base-squadFR-fquad-piaf (HuggingFace, 2023).
- Italian: anakin87/electra-italian-xxl-cased-squad-it (GitHub, 2023).
- Spanish: PlanTL-GOB-ES/roberta-base-bne-sqac (HuggingFace, 2023).

All these models are freely accessible and available on the official website of the HuggingFace project.

The above models return answers explicitly contained in the text, which provides enough security to the user about the reliability of the information provided by the system. However, in many cases the answer that the user is looking for is not explicitly formulated in any particular sentence. In these cases, the question-answer models do not return any information, so they are not very useful.

To solve this issue, the latest version of MetaQuarry has integrated a Large Language Model such as Mixtral¹ that allows Abstractive Questions Answering in the languages supported by the project.

Question-answering models have as input, a question, but also a context. The quality of the response therefore depends on two aspects:

- Quality of the prompt. The prompt is the instruction or script someone gives to the model. In the case of Mixtral it is important to specify by means of an appropriate instruction that the answer must be limited to the context provided, obtained from the set of selected documents and the appropriate language. Different versions of the prompt were tested until we found one that minimized *hallucinations*: text that the model responds to based on information other than that provided in the context.
- Context quality: It is important to accurately select the documents that we provide to the model as a context. If the context provided to the Question Answering model is too small, the model will not find a suitable answer; if it's too big, you won't be able to process it due to the algorithm's limitations.

	<p>Depending on the type of documents processed by MetaQuarry (number of pages per document, number of words per page, information in tables, text in images, etc.), we will have to define a longer or shorter context.</p> <p>The context for the question-answering model is obtained from the most relevant n-documents returned by the search engine, therefore, the quality of the answer ultimately depends on the quality of the search engine.</p> <p>Advanced Search Engine</p> <p>The search engine is based on the open-source Apache SolR platform written in Java. The main function of the search engine is to index documents and other sources of information so that they are available from the search engine, once the indexing module has been properly configured. Therefore, this component is responsible for performing both functionalities: the indexing of the information and the retrieval of results.</p> <p>The functionalities provided by the search engine are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Import <p>From the credentials entered by the user in the local database to using the MetaQuarry configuration tool, the system has access to the documents shared by the user on the various platforms: Google Drive, Microsoft SharePoint or OwnCloud. The documents supported by the system are the most common formats of Microsoft Office and Open Office packages: DOC, DOCX, XLS, XLSX, PPT etc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Extract text <p>Once the documents have been temporarily downloaded, the text contained in them extracted. To do this, the SolR Tika library is used. This tool allows you not only to extract text from the formats mentioned above, but also to process scanned PDF documents and images containing text using OCR optical character recognition technology.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Index <p style="padding-left: 40px;">The text extracted from each document is indexed using the Solr search engine. If the documents are pageable if they are in: PDF or PPT. Each page is indexed separately to make context selection more efficient. Otherwise, all the document text is indexed in a single entry. In total, the VICAT search engine database contains 914 entries.</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">If documents are modified or deleted, these documents are automatically updated or removed from the index so that they will not appear as results for new searches.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Target Audience</p>	<p>This service is aimed at helping the quarry managers and operators search in a heterogeneous database of documents for any relevant information they would need for the day-to-day operation of the quarry, quickly finding via natural language queries text and information “hidden” in almost any type of document (images, scanned pdf, word, power point presentations, excel files, etc.)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Hardware Requirements</p>	<p>For this service there is no specific hardware requirement for the quarry if used with the cloud solution form SIGMA. A terminal with internet access is good enough and significant storage capacity is needed if documentation is handled locally.</p>

	<p>In order to deploy the solution at Sigma premises, a server with two GPUs with 48GB each, for example NVIDIA A6000, is necessary.</p> <p>At the software level, the proposed system is composed of a series of components described below, which will be deployed using open-source Docker technology:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Front-end/Firewall (Apache web server). 2) Web Interface Framework (Streamlit-python). 3) User database (SQLite / PostgreSQL). 4) Search Engine (Apache Solr) 5) Language Models server (vLLM) 6) Component Virtualizer (Docker).
<p>Installation Process</p>	<p>To use MetaQuarry, there is no installation required on site for users. It is implemented as a web application and a link is all that is required together with an internet connection.</p>
<p>Communication Protocols -</p>	<p>For the MetaQuarry service, there are no specific connections between devices. Internet protocols are needed to access the web server (HTTPS, basically). The document store implementation depends on the quarry choices, but normally they are implemented on specific commercial platforms as explained above.</p>
<p>Data Storage & Management</p>	<p>MetaQuarry can handle a cloud or on-site solution Data security is provided basically by the cloud service providers: Google Drive, Microsoft SharePoint or OwnCloud.</p>
<p>AI Integration & Implementation</p>	<p>For the MetaQuarry service the deployment is being performed on the SIGMA's infrastructure. One server has been scaled taking into consideration the amount of information provided for the pilots, in this case VICAT, but also HOLCIM has been using the service. The deployment architecture is shown below:</p> <pre> graph TD User[User Laptop] -- http://0.0.0.0:8501 --> Streamlit subgraph Ubuntu subgraph Docker Streamlit PostgreSQL spaCy Solr[Apache Solr] end vLLM end Streamlit <--> PostgreSQL Streamlit <--> spaCy Streamlit <--> Solr Solr --> vLLM vLLM --> GPU1[GPU] vLLM --> GPU2[GPU] </pre>

Figure 21 MetaQuarry deployment architecture

The different service web interface pages are shown below:

Figure 22 MetaQuarry user interface (“Questions”)

Application Features

The application basically has four windows, one named “Questions” that is being used to insert a query in natural language as shown in the figure above. Then there is the second page named “Testing” that is used to learn how to use the tool by providing example queries relative to the type of documentation handled in VICAT.

Figure 23 Metaquarry user interface (“Testing”)

The third page, “Documents”, show the available document library as a list. The user can verify what kind of information is being processed by the tool.

Documents

Your indexed documents are listed here

	Name	Last Modified	Source
0	%28Draft%29-DIGIECOQUARRY-D1.4.docx	2021-11-19T07:55:50Z	owncloud
1	1+consigne+AT.doc	2010-06-04T12:02:53Z	owncloud
2	2+consigne+alcoo.doc	2009-10-09T08:24:01Z	owncloud
3	2012-01+DRPE+Fenouillet.xls	2012-01-31T17:21:36Z	owncloud
4	2013-01+DRPE+Fenouillet.xls	2013-01-23T10:53:41Z	owncloud
5	2014-01+DRPE+Fenouillet.xls	2014-01-30T08:16:31Z	owncloud
6	2014-12+EDR+Fenouillet.xls	2015-10-01T13:34:53Z	owncloud
7	2015-02+DRPE+Fenouillet.xls	2015-02-17T15:04:34Z	owncloud
8	2015-09+DRPE+Fenouillet.xls	2015-09-28T14:16:56Z	owncloud
9	2015-12+EDR+Fenouillet.xls	2016-01-11T08:28:40Z	owncloud
10	2016-10+DRPE+Fenouillet.xls	2016-10-04T09:27:38Z	owncloud
11	2016-12+EDR+Fenouillet.xls	2017-01-11T08:37:30Z	owncloud
12	2017-10+DRPE+Fenouillet.xlsx	2017-10-20T09:11:34Z	owncloud
13	2017-12+EDR+Fenouillet.xls	2018-01-15T14:06:37Z	owncloud
14	2018-10+DRPE+Fenouillet.xlsx	2018-10-24T09:02:15Z	owncloud
15	2018-12+EDR+Fenouillet.xls	2019-01-18T14:09:42Z	owncloud
16	2019-09+DRPE+Fenouillet.xlsx	2019-09-24T09:16:48Z	owncloud
17	2019-12+EDR+Fenouillet.xls	2020-02-20T14:02:57Z	owncloud
18	2020-11+EvRP+Fenouillet.xls	2022-02-15T09:13:33Z	owncloud

Figure 24 MetaQuarry user interface (“Documents”)

And finally, there is a fourth “Configuration” page which guides the user on how to include databases/ cloud storage for their documentation that they use internally. This for three commercial solutions:

- Google drive
- Sharepoint
- Owncloud

Configuration

You can integrate MetaQuarry with the following platforms

Google Drive SharePoint **OwnCloud**

Instructions

1. Use the credentials from your OwnCloud service and select the Folder you want to index.

url

Folder

User

Password

Figure 25 MetaQuarry user interface (“Configuration”)

For each of the three solutions detailed instructions are included.

The link that is used to access the MeataQuarry tool for VICAT is:

<https://sigmatag.sigma-ai.com/vicat/>

The latter is protected with specific credentials.

Security & Compliance

The data from the quarries that is processed will always be protected by the main cloud storage solution that is chosen by the customer. These tools strictly follow state of the art technologies to secure the information and control the authentication process. The latter data (files, documents, etc.) is not sent to any server outside the control of the quarry.

<p>Performance Metrics</p>	<p>The most important metric for such a service is the accuracy in answering and finding the information the user is looking for. The overall accuracy obtained for the VICAT set of documentation using MetaQuarry is 78%.</p>										
<p>Support & Maintenance</p>	<p>The system is very stable, and up until now the support needed has been minimal. Deployment is autonomous and can be also operated remotely. Troubleshooting until now has needed almost no effort. With respect to maintenance, only server maintenance is needed when detecting issues with their performance, mostly due to memory occupation performance and latency. Until now, no overloading situation has been observed, since the amount of data handled is limited in the pilots. The more information is handled, the better the system dimensioning that must be performed.</p>										
<p>Business Model & Pricing</p>	<p>Given the complexity of the technologies developed by the company, commercial management and technical management have always gone hand in hand, both in Sigma's early days and today, to create the sales strategy that Sigma has defined for the commercialization of a new product. As a guideline, the following revenue model is established that will have to be adjusted according to the knowledge acquired in the pilot, and after a more in-depth analysis of market potential. Compared to the initial strategy, prices have been revised due to the current data processing requirements, which have experienced a very significant increase due to the use of LLM models: Pricing associated with Deployment SET-UP: includes the deployment of the platform and integration with the documentary sources to carry out indexing of the documents. Depending on the complexity, a range ranging from €10,000 to €20,000 is forecast. ANNUAL MAINTENANCE: 3.000€. PLATFORM LICENSING: a scenario of user steps is conceived, with indicative prices (monthly payment) according to the following table:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="427 1032 1431 1281"> <thead> <tr> <th>Users</th> <th>Monthly price</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>From 1 to 100</td> <td>500€</td> </tr> <tr> <td>From 101 to 300</td> <td>800€</td> </tr> <tr> <td>From 301 to 1000</td> <td>1.200€</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Corporate (more than 1000)</td> <td>1.500€</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Users	Monthly price	From 1 to 100	500€	From 101 to 300	800€	From 301 to 1000	1.200€	Corporate (more than 1000)	1.500€
Users	Monthly price										
From 1 to 100	500€										
From 101 to 300	800€										
From 301 to 1000	1.200€										
Corporate (more than 1000)	1.500€										
<p>Competitive Advantage</p>	<p>MetaQuarry will hinge on a modular architecture composed mainly of two components: search engine and web application, now enriched with the use of an LLM model, with which an advanced semantic search tool capable of using natural language as input is implemented.</p> <p>Compared to the solutions present on the market, MetaQuarry has a strong competitive advantage, as it is a new solution that ranges from indexing content to the search engine that will allow the content to be retrieved.</p> <p>In addition, it is a multilingual solution, which analyses content of various types: word, excel, pdf, images, etc. On the other hand, deployment is flexible, it can be on-site or connected through APIs on Sigma's servers, as has been also done in the project.</p> <p>Likewise, the existing solutions on the market today generally do not yet provide a search using natural language but are based on keywords or literal language in the case of search engines implemented in web portals, so MetaQuarry is a very attractive solution for this type of solutions.</p>										

	With MetaQuarry, the daily exploitation of the document base is facilitated by being able to obtain the information in a more intuitive and direct way.
Future Enhancements	<p>The accuracy of the solution depends now on the LLM technologies employed. And certainly, the model used is key. At the moment, MIXTRAL is being used. But further enhancements can be achieved by using for example the DEEPSEEK MODEL. The latter is still being tested at SIGMA to analyze its performance.</p> <p>Other improvements could be also carried out by applying prompt engineering, introducing a tool that will guide the user on how to better generate queries, using vectorial databases instead of indexation by SolR, or LLM models specialized in Questions-Answering tasks over table information.</p>

2.7.2.2 Activities performed since November 2023

Basically, for Metaquarry, only modelling improvements were implemented by using the MIXTRAL LLM model which improved considerably the accuracy of the results.

Moreover, the user interface was also improved in terms of the information and parameters that are shown to the users as explained in the above table.

Also a detailed evaluation was carried out to assess the accuracy of the models used to answer the queries.

Table 3 Metaquarry queries example.

Question	Answer	Found in doc. Number
Qu'est-ce qu'il faut faire si quelqu'un s'est fait électrocuter?	En présence d'une personne électrocutée, il faut immédiatement couper l'interrupteur général avant toute intervention. Ensuite, il est important d'alerter les secours en composant le numéro d'urgence approprié et de protéger et rassurer la ou les personnes blessées. Il est également recommandé de ne pas toucher ni déplacer la personne blessée sauf en cas de danger imminent.	1
Qui est-ce que peut effectuer des contrôles d'alcoolémie ?	Le Chef de secteur peut effectuer des contrôles d'alcoolémie à toute heure de la journée.	1
Comment est-ce qu'il est effectué le remplissage des trémies?	Le remplissage des trémies est effectué comme suit: - Trémies A et B : Par chargeur.	1
Qui est l'agent de maîtrise responsable des travaux à l'intérieur des silos?	L'agent de maîtrise responsable des travaux à l'intérieur des silos est JEAN-MISTAL.\n"	1
A qui est-ce qu'il faut informer d'un accident grave survenu sur le chantier ?	Il faut immédiatement informer le Directeur Régional de l'Industrie, de la Recherche et de l'Environnement (DREAL) en cas d'accident grave ou mortel sur le chantier. Le numéro à composer pour joindre le DREAL est le 05 61 15 39 99.	1

Qui est-ce que peut effectuer l'ouverture des orifices d'évacuation d'une trémie ?	L'ouverture des orifices d'évacuation d'une trémie ne doit être effectuée que par le personnel compétent et autorisé."	?
Quelle est la vitesse maximale autorisée sur le site?	La vitesse maximale autorisée sur le site est de 30 km/h.	1
À quelle périodicité doit le conducteur d'un camion de stockage effectuer le graissage des articulations ?	Le conducteur d'un camion doit effectuer le graissage des articulations toutes les 50 heures de conduite.	1
À quelle périodicité doit le conducteur d'un camion de stockage effectuer la vidange moteur ?	La vidange moteur doit être effectuée tous les 250 heures de fonctionnement pour un camion de stockage.	?
Quelles sont les seuils retenus pour quantifier le risque d'une explosion ?	Answer not found in this repository.	?
Quelle directive européenne règle l'évaluation d'un risque d'explosion ?	La Directive 1999/92/CE du Conseil intitulée : « Prescriptions minimales visant à améliorer la protection en matière de sécurité et de santé des travailleurs susceptibles d'être exposés au risque d'atmosphères explosives ».	1
Qui est autorisé à intervenir en zone ATEX?	Seules les personnes ayant été formées sont autorisées à intervenir en zone ATEX.	5
Qu'est-ce que la limite supérieure d'explosivité?	La limite supérieure d'explosivité est la concentration dans l'air de gaz, ou vapeur inflammable, au-dessus de laquelle l'atmosphère gazeuse n'est pas explosive.	1
Quel est le numéro pour alerter les pompiers ?	Le numéro pour alerter les pompiers est le 18.	1
Quelle est l'adresse du site ?	L'adresse du site est : Route de Paris, 31150 FENOUILLET.	1
Où est-ce que trouver un défibrillateur ?	Un défibrillateur est présent au Décathlon à côté du site de Fenouillet.	1

2.8 Development of H&S systems for stationary equipment (Task 5.1 and 5.2)

2.8.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	AI based Person detection System
Overview	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - VICAT expressed interest in monitoring a specific area of their site where vehicle movement and personnel interaction posed a collision risk.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system architecture and the corresponding system features are displayed in figure xx below. It is based on improving safety by informing about critical situations.
Key Components	The components are laid out in Deliverable 5.1
Target Audience	<p>Different stakeholders will benefit from this solution:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Workers working in hazardous situations will be informed - Operators who get a report about the amount of hazardous situations reported.
Hardware Requirements	The hardware is described in Deliverable 5.1
Installation Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - As we set-up different field of views, depending on the site requirements, we need to be present at the site to support our partners.
Communication Protocols	Based on Cellular network (3G)
Data Storage & Management	Except for the number of person detection in IQS, we do not store any data.
AI Integration & Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For this use case, only AI makes sense, as it is much more performant than classical algorithms (see also DEQ Deliverable 5.1). - We evaluated different Networks and trained (and validated) and have now a Deep learning Model that does not need much hardware power and is therefore very performant.
Application Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The core consideration were to improve the safety of the workers. Therefore, we took various steps to increase the robustness of the system, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Testing different AI Models, using one of the most performant. o Using context analysis and object tracking to improve performance o Use Hardware, which can be used in an rough outdoor environment (and lock it). o Keep the system simple.
Security & Compliance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hardware is locked (and protected via key) - No data storage - No external interface except connection to IQS and ITK.

Performance Metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Since the last update (beginning of March) very stable - For Metrics see Result section
Support & Maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ongoing support, if problems occur.
Business Model & Pricing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Currently, we are in discussions about the pricing model with different stakeholders, among one industrialization partner from the machine manufacturer and several quarries and ready-mix concrete operators.
Competitive Advantage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Due to the training of AI specifically for quarries and ready-mix concrete operators, we received the feedback from our partners that for this field of view and with that performance not many systems are usable.
Future Enhancements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The speed of development for (AI) applications is constantly increasing. As ITK has set-up an pipeline for AI development we hope to be able to provide our DEQ partners also in the future with the developments concerning AI. - It can be expected that the noise of the alert might be too quiet. Besides using a louder alert, it would be possible to develop a solution that sends directly a message to a device (e.g. smartphone or machine).

2.8.2 Activities since November 2023

The following passage is from Deliverable 5.1:

“Having gained the experience with prototyping the PoC-System for Heidelberg Materials and connected to that having set-up the framework as described in the previous chapters, a visit at VICAT was conducted by ITK in September 2023 to expand the system as described in the Grand Agreement.

For VICAT the surveillance of the mud area was identified as system expansion in the first step. Yet, after several discussions it turned out that a surveillance of the area before the conveyor is sounder. The idea is to warn with an acoustic sound in case a person is detected entering the defined area before the machine.

As the use cases, the requirements and the corresponding architecture are very much comparable to the prototype installed at the scraper plant, a lot of the already known software/hardware was installed; it is currently running on an Basler Camera at the top of the conveyor has an acoustic alert (Backup and Reverse Warning Alarms) from Brigade an NVIDIA ORIN Board and a running Team-Viewer license (in order to check for ITK from abroad on the system and install e.g. updates.). In April 2024 the installation took place at VICAT.

Figure 26 Pictures from the installation at VICAT.

The field of view of the camera is displayed below. Seeing the different perspective of the camera, the algorithm described above will need to be adapted slightly to the use case”

Figure 27: View of the camera

The architecture of the system and the corresponding features does look like described in Figure 41:

The camera first detects a scene, then various AI models are being used (e.g. including one for object tracking) and then an acoustic alert is triggered informing the workers to not be present in that area. The amount of detected persons is sent via 3G to the IQS, where a counter of the detections is activated, giving constantly the operator the possibility to monitor safety indicators.

Figure 28 Stages of the processing of data

The AI algorithm for the VICAT installation was adapted and improved using a dedicated AI pipeline. This pipeline facilitated efficient data acquisition, labeling, training, and validation. New data was collected, capturing the specific environment, camera perspective, and potential hazard scenarios. This data was then labeled using established guidelines, ensuring high-quality ground truth for training the AI model.

Leveraging this new dataset, the object detection model was retrained. The training process incorporated data augmentation techniques to enhance the model's robustness and generalization capabilities. Performance was rigorously evaluated throughout the training process using relevant metrics (see result section). This iterative process allowed for continuous optimization of the model and its hyperparameters. The resulting retrained model demonstrated significant improvement in object detection accuracy and a reduction in false negatives, enhancing the safety and reliability of the system at the VICAT site. The updated model was then deployed to the VICAT installation via an over-the-air update.

2.9 Simulation model for environment and safety indicators

2.9.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	[Insert Service Name]
Overview	Brief summary of the service and its purpose.
Key Components	Hardware Installation: Setting up physical infrastructure. Communications: Enabling data transmission and network integration. - Data Storage: Secure cloud or on-premises storage solutions. - AI Implementation: Deploying AI-driven applications for automation and insights.
Target Audience	Define the industries or customers that benefit from this service.
Hardware Requirements	List of necessary devices (e.g., sensors, servers, IoT devices, networking equipment).
Installation Process	Step-by-step hardware setup and integration process.
Communication Protocols -	Types of communication technologies used (e.g., 5G, Wi-Fi, Ethernet, LoRa). - Data transmission security measures.
Data Storage & Management	- Storage solutions (cloud, hybrid, on-premises). - Data security, backup, and compliance considerations.
AI Integration & Implementation	- AI models used (e.g., machine learning, deep learning, NLP, computer vision). - How AI enhances application functionality (automation, predictions, analytics).
Application Features	- Core functionalities of the AI-powered application. - User interface and user experience design considerations.
Security & Compliance	- Cybersecurity measures to protect hardware and data. - Compliance with industry regulations (GDPR, HIPAA, etc.).
Performance Metrics	- KPIs to measure success (e.g., system uptime, AI model accuracy, data processing speed).
Support & Maintenance	- Ongoing technical support, updates, and troubleshooting processes.
Business Model & Pricing	- Subscription-based, pay-per-use, or one-time purchase pricing models.
Competitive Advantage	How this service stands out compared to competitors.
Future Enhancements	- Planned upgrades or AI improvements.

2.9.2 Activities performed since November 2023

The data was updated and transferred to Chalmers in order to compare the 2019 pre-project data and the current data for the year 2024.

An analysis is being carried out by Chalmers

2.10 Quarry Voices on Technology Deployment

The following section presents a structured interview conducted by ANEFA, as the coordinator of the DigiEcoQuarry project. The interview aimed to gather qualitative feedback from representatives of Vicat concerning the technologies implemented at their site. The primary objectives included assessing overall perception, operational impacts, observed benefits, key success factors, potential barriers, and suggestions for future enhancements. Insights gained from this discussion provide valuable understanding regarding the effectiveness of technological innovations developed by the project, their replicability within the industry, and their alignment with broader sustainability goals.

1. Overall Perception

General assessment of the implemented technologies

The implementation of new technologies in the quarry has brought several positive advancements, significantly enhancing operational efficiency and sustainability. The integration of digital tools has improved data collection and monitoring, allowing for more informed decision-making. Notably, the mobile crusher has demonstrated a substantial reduction in noise levels and dust emissions due to its integrated water spray system. This improvement contributes to a more environmentally friendly operation while also creating a better working environment for employees.

Although some technologies are still in the early stages of full implementation, the general consensus is that they have great potential. The monitoring platform for environmental and safety indicators is a particularly promising tool, ensuring greater transparency and control over key sustainability metrics. Moreover, the adoption of digital dashboards has facilitated better tracking of production and resource management, which will lead to long-term efficiency gains.

Added value to daily operations

The introduction of digitalization and automation has significantly enhanced the daily operations of the quarry. The ability to centralize key production data into a single dashboard has simplified operational oversight, reducing the need for manual data entry and improving accuracy. Furthermore, the improved monitoring of stock levels and material flows has streamlined logistics, contributing to optimized resource allocation.

Additionally, social acceptance initiatives have been successfully implemented, fostering better relationships with the local community. The creation of visitor facilities, including a dedicated observation platform, has enhanced engagement with stakeholders and demonstrated a commitment to transparency and sustainability.

2. Key Benefits Observed

Operational efficiency (improved productivity, resource optimization, etc.): The adoption of digital dashboards and real-time monitoring systems has enhanced productivity by providing a clearer overview of operational performance. The integration of automated data collection tools has improved the accuracy of production tracking, reducing manual workload and ensuring better planning.

The mobile crusher has played a crucial role in optimizing resource efficiency by lowering fuel consumption and minimizing emissions. Furthermore, advancements in stock management have facilitated better control over material supply chains, ensuring continuous and well-coordinated operations.

Environmental impact (enhanced sustainability, reduced emissions, etc.): A key achievement has been the successful reduction of environmental impact through innovative technology. The mobile crusher's water spray system has significantly decreased dust emissions, improving air quality in and around the site. This not only benefits workers but also aligns with the company's broader sustainability goals.

Additionally, the continuous monitoring of environmental indicators has provided valuable insights into resource consumption and emissions. This data will support further improvements in sustainability practices and compliance with regulatory standards.

Workplace safety: The implementation of digital monitoring systems has contributed to a safer working environment by reducing the need for manual checks in potentially hazardous areas. The improved visibility of key operational data has allowed for proactive risk management, helping to prevent workplace incidents.

Moreover, investments in social infrastructure, such as improved facilities for employees, reflect a strong commitment to workplace well-being. These initiatives have not only enhanced safety but also increased employee satisfaction and engagement.

Digitalisation: The digitalisation of operational processes has led to more efficient decision-making by providing comprehensive and real-time insights. The implementation of data dashboards has streamlined reporting procedures, allowing management to make informed choices based on accurate and up-to-date information.

By integrating digital tools into daily workflows, operational bottlenecks have been reduced, leading to a more agile and adaptive approach to quarry management. As these systems continue to evolve, they will further enhance strategic planning and performance optimisation.

3. Success Factors and Adoption Potential

Ease of integration and user-friendliness: The newly implemented technologies have been designed with user-friendliness in mind, ensuring that staff can adopt them with minimal training. The dashboards, in particular, have been well-received for their intuitive interface and accessibility.

Replicability across different quarry sites: Many of the solutions introduced in this project have strong potential for replication across other quarry sites. Digital dashboards, environmental monitoring systems, and optimised stock management techniques can be effectively deployed in different operational environments, ensuring widespread efficiency gains.

Contribution to industry innovation: This project has demonstrated the significant role that technological advancements can play in modern quarrying operations. By leveraging digitalisation and automation, the industry is moving towards a more efficient and sustainable future. The successful implementation of these technologies serves as a benchmark for further innovation across the sector.

Barriers to adoption: While most technologies have been well received, their integration into existing operational frameworks requires careful planning. Continued investment in training and adaptation will ensure that employees can fully harness the benefits of these tools. As the industry continues to embrace digitalisation, these initial challenges will be progressively overcome.

4. Future Outlook

Recommendations and opportunities for further optimisation: The next step in optimising quarry operations lies in expanding the use of artificial intelligence (AI) for logistics and resource management. AI-driven solutions can improve traffic flow within the site, enhancing the coordination of vehicle movements and reducing waiting times. Additionally, the integration of QR-based navigation systems can facilitate more efficient material distribution.

Long-term implementation prospects: Looking ahead, the full integration of BIM technology and predictive maintenance tools will be a priority. These innovations will enable enhanced asset management and preventive maintenance strategies, reducing downtime and extending the lifespan of critical equipment.

The continued development of digital dashboards will further streamline operations by consolidating real-time data from multiple sources into a single interface. This will allow for better resource allocation and more precise performance monitoring.

Alignment with the sector's sustainability goals: The quarry's commitment to sustainability is reinforced by the successful adoption of these technologies. The improvements in dust and noise reduction, combined with the enhanced tracking of environmental indicators, demonstrate a clear alignment with sustainability objectives.

As the company advances its Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) strategy, these tools will play a vital role in ensuring compliance with environmental standards and fostering transparent communication with stakeholders. By maintaining this momentum, the quarry will continue to be at the forefront of sustainable and responsible industry practices.

3 Results

This chapter summarises the main results achieved in VICAT pilot site.

3.1 Results on Innovative Crusher

3.1.1 New hybrid powertrain

Due to the nature of the crushed material in VICAT, the total load power exhibited high variance and peaks. The hybrid system could be controlled during crushing, and the battery was successfully utilized to cover the power peaks in VICAT. Similar observations were made during the pre-tests in Finland (reported in D2.9). Nevertheless, the feed material in VICAT was significantly more challenging for the crusher, and both average power (142 kW) and peak power (up to 299 kW) were higher than the corresponding values in the pre-tests.

During the development and simulation of the new hybrid powertrain, a reduction in fuel usage per ton was expected compared to old diesel-electric powertrain. However, when comparing to older data, the new hybrid powertrain did not reach the reductions in fuel consumption during the piloting week. Despite this, several benefits of the new powertrain were identified. The performance improvements related to high loads could, in broader context, impact overall CO₂ emissions by reducing them. It should be emphasized that this is still speculative and not in the direct scope of the project. In summary, Metso finds the results achieved in VICAT valuable, and the piloting of the entirely new powertrain can be considered successful. In the future, the performance of the powertrain can be further improved by optimizing various components of the mobile crusher based on the gathered data and observations.

3.1.2 Dust minimization

The overall dust level during the piloting week in VICAT was very low, PM₁₀ < 800 µm/m³, due to weather conditions and moisture of the crushed material. During crushing, it was observed that most of the visible dust originated from the feeding excavator actions, which are not within the scope of the machine's dust suppression system. The dust suppression system (water spraying) was used during crushing and reference measurements were taken when the spraying system was not in use, but the crushing process was ongoing. The two different water spraying pressures were tested, and the water consumption could be accurately measured for the system: 3 liters/minute for the 40 bars spraying and 7.7 liters/minute for the 150 bars spraying.

Initial visual observations indicated that the spraying had no significant effect on the dust levels. This was later confirmed in the data in results analysis phase. Dust concentration maps are shown in Figures 18 and 19 for cases without and with dust suppression. Water ponds in the ground are seen in the same images. In conclusion, the efficiency of the dust suppression could not be validated in VICAT due to the low dust levels. In the pre-tests in Finland (reported in D2.9) dust reduction rate of 64 % was achieved with the same system. The difference was the crushed material, that was in the Finnish pilot mixture of granite and limestone. The material used in the test in Finland had less moisture, and different weather conditions also made it possible to evaluate the water spraying system performance.

Figure 29. Dust (PM10) concentration map for reference with no dust suppression system active on mobile crusher.

Figure 30. Dust (PM10) concentration map when dust suppression system is working with 150 bar pressure.

3.1.3 Noise minimization

The machine was equipped with the noise encapsulations detailed in D2.9. The measurement system for areal mapping of noise pressure in decibels was adapted in measuring the noise levels in VICAT piloting site. A noise map was created during crushing in VICAT, as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** The red line in the map marks the area where noise level exceeds 85 dB, which is considered a dangerous limit for workers. This map indicates the situation when the noise suppression systems are already installed on the machine. Unfortunately, due to interruptions in the crushing process, Metso was unable to perform part of the planned noise measurements. Therefore, the reference measurement that could provide the baseline (noise level without the encapsulations) is not available for the piloting week in VICAT.

Figure 31. Noise map with the noise encapsulation covers of the mobile crusher in use in VICAT.

Noise measurements with the same encapsulations were performed also in the mobile crusher pre-tests in Finland. The noise maps for two scenarios were created in pre-tests: noise covers open (giving the reference value) (a) and noise covers closed (b), both presented in Figure 32. There was no significant difference between the two cases and overall noise levels were higher than expected. It was later found that in this measurement set, the noise from the cooling fan of the diesel engine was dominant. The noise levels of the machine were lowered significantly later by replacing an old engine radiator with a new and clean unit, reducing the need for cooling air volume and thereby lowering the rotational velocity of the cooling fan, lowering noise levels. As a conclusion, potentially significant noise source was identified, but the efficiency of the noise encapsulations could not be verified.

Figure 32. Noise map with the noise encapsulation covers of the mobile crusher a) open on one side, b) all in use.

The main result from the noise in VICAT pilot is the determination of the average 85 dB(A) distance from the mobile crusher that was calculated from the measurement data. **The distance is 14.3 meters.** We were unable to measure the noise reduction efficiency of the noise encapsulations at the VICAT site due to technical challenges with the measurements. The application (feed material) and power level of the machine remain major factors in the total noise level. Identifying noise sources and their roles is critical, and simultaneously, the crushing events with demolition waste are often very unpredictable in nature. Setting up a repeatable and reliable noise measurements for the crushing event remains very challenging.

3.2 Results on Weighting systems

The weighing systems installed on-site ensure reliable production data collection for products transported on conveyors that were initially not equipped with scales.

Thanks to these two devices, we now have increased accuracy in tracking production volumes. This also allows us to better anticipate material needs when customers place aggregate orders. Indeed, we can now quantify hourly production in real time, providing better visibility into the time required to meet demands.

Additionally, this system enables us to gain a better understanding of our raw materials by sending this data directly to the dashboard, which compiles all relevant information.

3.2 Results and experiences on Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS)

At the Vicat site, a data management platform (CDMP) utilizing data lake technologies has been deployed and is operational (<https://cdmp.vicat.confidential.eu/>). This platform collects daily data from various quarry processes, including automation (Scada), environment, health & safety (H&S), and mobile crushers. These data are accessible to users and expert systems.

Data from the Scada system is collected by a dedicated service, enabling the generation of dashboards for monitoring quarry production data. Data from the mobile crusher is collected by a dedicated service, allowing the tracking of productivity and efficiency indicators. Data from the H&S system is collected by a dedicated service, facilitating the monitoring of safety indicators. Data from the Plantsmith system is collected by a dedicated service, enabling the tracking of environmental performance across over 30 impact categories.

All data are accessible through a unique Application deployed in the Azure cloud. These tools break down data silos and facilitate data integration from diverse sources, enhancing decision-making capabilities and performance monitoring using the Business Management Tools of the IQS shown below.

Figure 33. Dashboard

These results demonstrate the successful implementation of the IQS project concept. This concept is highly adaptable for integrating new indicators useful for quarry management and facilitating decision-making mechanisms.

3.3 Results related to Development of H&S systems for stationary equipment (Task 5.1 and 5.2)

Having safety identified as one of the core objectives of DEQ we have installed here an AI based system that informs the direct involved workers and the operators via a dashboard when they are walking around in an area, where no person should be present.

In general, when interpreting the performance of AI one must balance certain KPI scores. Here a short insertion about the logic behind it. Below in table 3 you see the different classes. On the left side “predicted class” means detected by the AI and on the top, “actual class” means ground truth (reality).

Of course, the worst case, is a false negative, meaning that our AI system did not recognize the person, despite the fact that there is a person. Yet, too many false positives, meaning that there is an alert despite the fact that there is no person lowers the acceptance of the system.

Table 4 AI logic

		Actual CLASS	
		True	False
Predicted CLASS	True	True Positives	False Positives (No person but alert)
	False	False Negatives (Person, but not alert)	True Negatives

In the field of AI, one often talks about “Thresholds”, meaning that how sure is the AI when detecting/classifying an object that this object is also there. Now the fine-tuning starts. For instance, if one recognizes a high level of false positives one can decrease the threshold on the costs that there will be an increase in false negatives. Currently we are working with a threshold of above 90%.

In this context, two valuable indicators for the performance of an AI algorithm are precision and recall. In this context, two valuable indicators for the performance of an AI algorithm are precision and recall. Precision answers the question of what percentage of the positive results predicted by the model are true positives. It helps to understand the proportion of true positives out of all predicted positive results (i.e., true positives and false positives).

Recall provides information about how many actual positive instances were correctly detected by the model. It is related to false negatives and true positives, not true negatives. Recall estimates the proportion of relevant positive instances that were detected.

Again, based on the idea of balancing, if one wants to increase recall, this will often come at the cost of precision (and vice versa). For both indicators, we have found reasonable balances, with both values above 90%.

The indicators are based per frame. Currently we are running on, depending on the setting, more than 10 frames per second. As we have some reaction time (and in order to decrease false positives), we defined, that there must be a detection for an object across four consecutive frames.

In general focussing on the performance of the AI and the system we are satisfied. Yet there are for further industrialization improvements to be made:

1. More Test and Validation needs to be carried out. Despite that we tested different corner cases and have good results in practise, more rigorous testing needs to be carried out here.
2. For our first PoC in Parsberg we used with the MultiSense S30 a different time, which was by the time nearly 10 times more expensive than the Basler Camera installed at CIMPOR. However, over the time the price of the MultiSense dropped considerably and we observe a much better performance by the MultiSense S30.

3. See above concerning the feature, informing the machine operators and the person walking around via additional devices.

3.4 Results on social acceptance strategy

Social acceptance is a major challenge for quarry operations, especially when located in the heart of a commercial area, in close proximity to the center of the Toulouse metropolitan area. In this context, the DEQ project has played a crucial role in improving our communication both internally, with Vicat Group employees, and externally, with local decision-makers.

Strengthening Internal Communication

To ensure optimal dissemination of information related to the DEQ project, numerous meetings, primarily informal, were organized to keep site employees informed about project progress and upcoming technologies.

Additionally, during the management meeting at the beginning of 2024, a general presentation of the DEQ project was conducted in the presence of sector personnel, certification managers from our laboratory, as well as Quality, Safety, and Environment managers.

Furthermore, several presentations were made during the Vicat Aggregates management committee meetings. This committee, composed of sector managers, regional directors, and process leaders (purchasing, human resources, finance, marketing, etc.), engaged in in-depth discussions about the opportunities offered by the project in the presence of the Director of Vicat Aggregates.

Actions Taken for External Communication

As part of our commitment to our external stakeholders, we organized and participated in several events to promote our professions and highlight the benefits of the DEQ project.

For instance, a quarry visit was organized for apprentices from the UNICEM CFA, providing them with an immersive experience of our activities and an opportunity to discover the contributions of the DEQ project to our site. Additionally, we participated in a student fair at the Louis Vicat High School in Souillac, where we presented the Vicat Group and our various professions.

Finally, an open day was held at the quarry, allowing local residents and decision-makers to gain a better understanding of our activities and discover our working environment.

4 Conclusion

The Digiecoquarry project has allowed us to explore the role that artificial intelligence could play in managing an aggregate quarry. Since the project's inception, we have deepened our understanding of this topic and identified its potential for improvement, both in production processes and environmental management, particularly in an urban setting like our site.

The applications of artificial intelligence are vast and enable optimization in several aspects of quarry operations. In terms of production, AI facilitates predictive maintenance through sensors capable of analyzing machine noise, as well as quality control via cameras that automatically adjust crusher settings. On the environmental side, AI can anticipate events such as strong wind peaks to limit dust dispersion.

Tested Technologies and Feedback

Among the technologies implemented or tested at our site, some have significantly improved working conditions for employees:

Securing Traffic Areas: The installation of cameras detecting pedestrian presence in equipment operation zones enables instant alerts for drivers, significantly reducing the risk of co-activity—an essential issue at a site like Fenouillet, where space is limited.

Optimizing Stock Monitoring: While stock calculation applications are effective, they are less suited to a quarry where inventories are conducted monthly. Technologies such as drones provide a more efficient alternative for these needs. However, this tool is particularly valuable for commercial teams or customers who need quick access to aggregate stock volumes.

Implementation of a Digital Dashboard: Creating a dashboard consolidating all quarry data and indicators represents a major advancement. Currently, information is scattered across different documents, making access sometimes complex. An interactive dashboard provides a comprehensive, real-time overview of site performance, covering production, energy and water consumption, and environmental impact. With just one click, the site manager can gain a clear vision of operations and make informed decisions.

Future Prospects and Strategic Challenges

The solutions introduced within the project have piqued the interest of several sector managers and regional directors at Granulats Vicat. The Group's strategy is moving towards an increasing digitalization of production tools, and this project has helped identify concrete levers to accelerate this transition. Some technologies could be tested in the near future, depending on the specific needs of different group entities.

Finally, this project is crucial for the sustainability of our activities. Quarries are often perceived as low-tech, polluting, and closed-off industries. However, they are an essential part of daily life. The successful completion of the Digiecoquarry project demonstrates that innovation can transform our sector by optimizing resource extraction, improving noise and dust emission management, and fully integrating environmental and social concerns.

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